

Protection of civilians during non-international armed conflicts and international human rights norms

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Abstract

Since the Second World War (WWII), the world has witnessed an increase in non-international armed conflicts (NIACs) around the world. These have caused enormous suffering for the civilian population. Yet the post WWII 1949 Geneva Conventions legal framework initially only consisted of one single Article - common Article 3 (CA3). This changed in 1977 with the adoption of Additional Protocol II (Protocol II). Nonetheless, the therein spelled out international humanitarian law (IHL) rules are rudimentary in comparison to those in international armed conflicts (IACs). Equally, the conduct of hostilities' IHL principles of limitation, military necessity, proportionality, distinction and good faith do not fully protect civilians and add a further layer of complexity in respect of the interplay with CA3, Protocol II and international human rights (IHR).

This is because IHR has developed separately from IHL, including *ius in bello*. Resultantly, IHL and IHR, despite sharing the common value of upholding humanity, have not properly evolved to form a coherent, united and robust legal framework to safeguard civilians.

Furthermore, customary IHL and IHR have only developed to a certain degree in respect of NIACs. Consequently, civilians have to experience undue hardship due to the weak legal framework founded in IHL, IHR, customary law and international law.

Moreover, those rights which have been afforded to civilians are difficult to put into effect since CA3 is silent on this, Protocol II is not sufficiently explicit and states can evoke human rights limitations, derogations and reservations. Whilst there exist diverse international oversight mechanisms, these have fundamental flaws which render the enforcement of IHL and IHR rather the exception than the rule. Only the most serious crimes are being punished, thereby creating a culture of impunity which tolerates low to medium-level atrocities against civilians during NIACs, including long-term environmental harm.

Abbreviations

ACHR	American Convention on Human Rights 1969
ACHPR	African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights
CA3	Common Article 3
Common Article 3	Common Article 3 to the four Geneva Conventions of 1949
ECHR	European Convention on Human Rights 1950
ECtHR	European Court of Human Rights
Convention III	Convention (III) Relative to the Treatment of Prisoners of War. Geneva, 12 August 1949
Convention IV	Convention (IV) relative to the Protection of Civilian Persons in Time of War, Geneva, 12 August 1949
ICC	International Criminal Court
ICESCR	International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights 1967
ICJ	International Court of Justice
ICCPR	International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights 1967
ICTY	International Criminal Tribunal for the former Yugoslavia
IHL	International Humanitarian Law
IHR	International Human Rights
ICRC	International Committee of the Red Cross
ICTR	International Criminal Tribunal for Rwanda
KFOR	Kosovo forces
NIAC	Non-international armed conflict
IAC	International armed conflict
Protocol I	Protocol Additional to the Geneva Conventions of 12 August 1949, and relating to the Protection of Victims of International Armed Conflicts (Protocol I)
Protocol II	Protocol Additional to the Geneva Conventions of 12 August 1949, and relating to the Protection of Victims of Non-International Armed Conflicts (Protocol II), 8 June 1977
UN	United Nations
UNGA	United Nations General Assembly
UNMIK	UN Mission in Kosovo
UNSC	United Nations Security Council
UNSCR	United Nations Security Council Resolution
US	United States
VCLT	Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties 1969
WWII	World War II

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Introduction

The research question which this dissertation seeks to answer is IHL and IHR safeguard civilians during NIACs. Recourse will be made particularly to IHR and the 1949 Geneva Conventions and Additional Protocols I and II, though limited reference is made to Hague law.¹ The central hypothesis/argument is that CA3 of the four Geneva Conventions of 1949, Protocol Additional to the Geneva Conventions of 12 August 1949, and relating to the Protection of Victims of Non-International Armed Conflicts (Protocol II), 8 June 1977 (Protocol II), customary law and IHR insufficiently protect civilians during NIACs. It is undoubtedly debatable what “insufficient protection for civilians during NIACs” means and the definition by the Inter-Agency Standing Committee’s of what is deemed “protection of civilians” has been adapted to describe the antonym as follows²: All legal gaps which exist within the protective regime which prevent that civilians are afforded all the rights as provided in purpose and literally by IHR, IHL, customary international law, as well as international law. The work thus focuses on the weaknesses in the law and implementation and enforcement of the law.

Indeed, the existing literature highlights that civilians during NIACs are not as much protected as civilians during international armed conflicts.³ This is because they cannot evoke the Convention (IV) relative to the Protection of Civilian Persons in Time of War, Geneva, 12 August 1949 (Convention IV) or Protocol Additional to the Geneva Conventions of 12

¹ The term Hague law denotes the Hague Conventions of 1899 and 1907 and the Hague Convention for the Protection of Cultural Property 1954 and the Second Protocol to the Hague Convention 1999, as further mentioned below at 1.2.

² Inter-Agency Standing Committee, *Manual on Field Practice in Internal Displacement*, Geneva, 1999; cited from Foreign & Commonwealth Office, Ministry of Defence, Department of International Development, UK Government Strategy on the Protection of Civilians in Armed Conflict, 2010, 1, 3 <https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/32950/ukstrategy-protect-civilians-arms-conflict.pdf> accessed 5th September 2015

³ See, for example, L. Perna, *The Formation of the Treaty Rules Applicable in Non-international Armed Conflicts* (Leiden, Koninklijke Brill NV 2006) 106

August 1949, and relating to the Protection of Victims of International Armed Conflicts (Protocol I), which particularly deal with civilian protection, as they only apply to international armed conflicts (IACs).⁴ Without the standards which govern armed conflicts being harmonised, civilians particularly suffer, especially because post WWII most armed conflicts have been of an internal nature.⁵ Since the start of the 20th century, there were over 250 such conflicts which have caused enormous suffering and the death of up to 170 million persons.⁶ For example, the atrocities perpetrated in the 90s in Rwanda, Liberia and Sierra Leone and the current conflicts in Ukraine and Syria bring to the fore the problem of a weak legal regime for NIACs.⁷ It is against this background that the dissertation seeks to holistically analyse the IHL and IHR frameworks in order to identify weaknesses which leave civilians unprotected during NIACs.

For the purpose of the study, the first chapter commences by analysing weaknesses within the legal definitions of key terms. For instance, the requirements to establish a NIAC in Protocol II are analysed in order to establish whether a too high threshold test has been set to meet the definition. It is scrutinised whether the way in which combatants and civilians and those, who should be protected, have been defined creates legal uncertainty. Subsequently, important conduct of hostilities principles are discussed, though as mentioned, the scope of the dissertation makes it not possible to also focus on Hague law. The discussion is therefore limited to the principles of limitation, military necessity, distinction, good faith and proportionality. Subsequently, issues which affect the protection of civilians during NIACs

⁴ C. Phuong, *The International Protection of Internally Displaced Persons* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press 2004) 45

⁵ B. O. Oswald, The Harmonization Project: Improving Compliance with the Law of War in Non-International Armed Conflicts, 53 *Columbia Journal of Transnational Law* 2014-2015, 105, 105

⁶ G. Fiddler, Using a Conditional Amnesty and Truth and Reconciliation as a Transitional Justice Mechanism in Syria, 47 *George Washington International Law Review* 2015, 893, 893

⁷ R. Arnold, Sivakumaran's 'Law of Non-International Armed Conflict': A Criminal Lawyer's Perspective, 48(2) *Israel Law Review* 2015, 253, 253

are assessed. Thereafter, CA3, Protocol II and customary IHL are examined in order to address whether they afford too little protective safeguards to civilians during NIACs.

The second chapter examines how civilians can be protected by IHR standards during NIACs. It therefore discusses important IHR values, for instance, enshrined in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) 1948 and identifies human rights which amount to *ius cogens* during NIACs. The notion of duty bearer is investigated, including whether non-state actors are held accountable. It is explored whether IHR is enforceable and to what extent the *lex specialis* principle undermines IHR. The limitations, derogations and reservations to IHR are discussed, including to what extent IHR can be suspended during a state of emergency i.e. in the case of a NIAC.

The third chapter assesses whether the domestic and international mechanisms are adequate to safeguard civilians. The international obligation of countries to undertake investigations and to pursue and punish offenders is investigated. It is explored to what extent the international oversight mechanisms protect civilians during NIACs. In this regard, common issues which undermine the effectiveness, for instance, of the United Nations (UN), the International Court of Justice (ICJ), the International Criminal Court (ICC), the International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC) and truth commissions, are highlighted.

The fourth chapter emphasises the importance of increasing legal protection for civilians during NIACs. Various other legal issues are discussed which impede the rights of civilians. For instance, it is considered whether the ability of the permanent five UN Security Council (UNSC) members to cast a veto has resulted in inaction or delays, which has endangered the lives of civilians during NIACs. Accountability issues in respect of the UN and UN authorised peacekeeping missions are described. Issues with establishing universal jurisdiction for grave breaches under the Geneva Convention regime and customary law are highlighted. The grant of amnesties is discussed. Other reasons for increasing legal protection

for civilians are provided. Accordingly, the rules which govern IHL and IHR during NIACs will be investigated, including deficiencies within the respective legal regimes which protect civilians.

Chapter 1: International humanitarian law (IHL) and the protection of civilians

1.0 Introduction

This chapter will analyse the applicable IHL rules, which safeguard civilians during armed conflicts. The analysis will also point out issues.

1.1 Defining key terms

The way in which a NIAC is defined has a profound impact since the protective safeguard for civilians can be disapplied when the definitional requirements cannot be met. Equally, the way in which combatants/fighters, specially protected persons and civilians are defined determines the scope of protection.

1.1.1 NIACs

For there to be an armed conflict, it has to be shown that there are “organised armed groups”, which conduct “fighting of some intensity.”⁸ A NIAC is an internal conflict, which is confined to the boundaries of one state and where non-state groups are involved in fighting with each other or with state groups. There is still a NIAC even when the state party receives assistance from other governments.⁹ However, the armed conflict can become “mixed” i.e. the non-international conflict may occur alongside an international conflict.¹⁰ Moreover, not all hostility is considered a NIAC, for instance, tension and internal disturbance, such as

⁸ T. D. Gill, R. Geiß, H. Krieger, T. McCormack, C. Paulussen, J. Dorsey, *Yearbook of International Humanitarian Law 2013* (The Hague, TMC Asser Press 2015) 224

⁹ H. Tonkin, *State Control over Private Military and Security Companies in Armed Conflict* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press 2011) 92

¹⁰ *Ibid* 93

sporadic and isolated violent acts and riots.¹¹ CA3 of the Geneva Conventions omits to include a definition for the term NIAC.¹² States are reluctant to acknowledge the existence of one since this can weaken their sovereignty; however, this weakens the effectiveness of international law and prevents that responsibility is assumed for domestic acts.¹³

There is not a body which is responsible for determining whether there is a NIAC, except when the International Court of Justice (ICJ) hears a case, the UNSC uses its Chapter VII powers of the UN Charter and passes a resolution or a Commission of Inquiry reaches such a conclusion, as happened, for instance, in respect of Libya.¹⁴ The failure to quickly decide whether there is a NIAC leaves civilians unprotected.

Civilians are especially vulnerable since not many international treaties regulate NIACs.¹⁵ Furthermore, states, which have not acceded to the relevant treaties, are only bound by virtue of customary international law.¹⁶ However, since the 1990s more customary international law has formed for NIACs.¹⁷ The ICJ¹⁸ explicated that CA3 sets out “elementary considerations

¹¹ Article 1(2) of the Protocol Additional to the Geneva Conventions of 12 August 1949, and relating to the Protection of Victims of NIACs (Protocol II), 8 June 1977 (Protocol II); Article 8(2)(d) &(f) of the Statute of the International Criminal Court Statute; F. Bouchet-Saulnier, L. Brav, C. Olivier, *The Practical Guide to Humanitarian Law* (2nd ed, Lanham, Rowman & Littlefield Publishers Inc 2007) 289

¹² A. Cullen, *The Concept of NIAC in International Humanitarian Law* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press 2010) 60-61

¹³ J. Summers, *Kosovo: A Precedent?: The Declaration of Independence, the Advisory Opinion and Implications for Statehood, Self-Determination and Minority Rights* (Leiden, Koninklijke Brill NV 2011) 242

¹⁴ Human Rights Council, Report of the International Commission of Inquiry on Libya, Nineteenth session, United Nations A/HRC/19/68, 2 March 2012, 1-15; J. Genser, B. S. Ugarte, *The United Nations Security Council in the Age of Human Rights* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press 2014) 408

¹⁵ Common Article 3 to the four Geneva Conventions of 12 August 1949 (CA3); Protocol II; Article 19 of the Hague Convention for the Protection of Cultural Property 1954 and the Second Protocol to the Hague Convention 1999; also see the Statute of the International Criminal Tribunal for Rwanda (ICTR) 1994; Article 8(2)(c)-(e) of the Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court 1998 (Rome Statute); Statute of International Criminal Tribunal for the Former Yugoslavia (ICTFY) 1992; Protocol for the Prohibition of the Use of Asphyxiating, Poisonous or Other Cases, and of Bacteriological Methods of Warfare 1925; Convention on the Prohibition of Military or Any Other Hostile Use of Environmental Modification Techniques 1977; Convention on Certain Conventional Weapons 1980; the Chemical Weapons Convention 1993; Mine Ban Convention 1997; Y. Dinstein, *Non-International Armed Conflicts in International Law* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press 2014) 8; D. Jinks, J. N. Maogoto, S. Solomon, *Applying International Humanitarian Law in Judicial and Quasi-Judicial Bodies, International and Domestic Aspects* (The Hague, TMC Asser Press 2014) 297

¹⁶ A. Enabulele, B. Bazuaye, *Teachings on Basic Topics in Public International Law* (Lagos, Ambik Press 2014) 122

¹⁷ S. Sivakumaran, *The Law of Non-International Armed Conflicts* (Oxford, Oxford University Press 2012) 55

of humanity”, which extend to NIACs.¹⁹ The ICJ observed that CA3 sets out “minimum rules applicable to international and to non-international conflicts.”²⁰ Hence, CA3 represents customary IHL and is applicable to all states, irrespective of ratification of the Geneva Conventions.

The concept of NIAC was further refined when Protocol II was adopted in 1977. It is not only required that such conflict takes place on the territory of a party, which has ratified the Protocol II,²¹ but Article 1(1) of Protocol II requires that the conflict is between organised armed groups or dissident armed forces and these have to be under a “responsible command” and control a part of the state, so that they can conduct concerted and sustained military activities. The Article requires that five criteria are met.²² Consequently, Protocol II does not govern conflicts in failed, weak or fragile states or situations where two rebel groups fight.²³ Hence, various internal conflicts escape Protocol II due to the high threshold requirements, thereby leaving civilians unprotected.²⁴

In *Prosecutor v Tadic*²⁵ (the *Tadic* case), it was explained that there have to be intense acts of violence by rebel groups which are conducted in an organised manner.²⁶ These two requirements make it possible to distinguish internal tensions and disturbances from a NIAC,

¹⁸ *Military and Paramilitary Activities In and Against Nicaragua (Nicaragua v United States of America)* [1986] I.C.J. Rep., p.14

¹⁹ *Ibid*, 218

²⁰ *Ibid*, 114; cited from n.15 (Dinstein) 10

²¹ CA3 of the Geneva Conventions of 12 August 1949; Article 1 of AP II

²² H. Fischer, A. McDonald, J. Dugard, *Yearbook of International Humanitarian Law - 2001* (The Hague, TMC Asser Press 2004) 142

²³ K. Watkin, A. J. Norris, *Non-International Armed Conflict in the Twenty-first Century* (Newport, International Law Studies 2012) 17; R. Geiss, Armed violence in fragile states: Low-intensity conflicts, spillover conflicts, and sporadic law enforcement operations by third parties, 91(873) *International Review of the Red Cross* 2009, 127-142, 128

²⁴ *Ibid* (Watkin)

²⁵ *Prosecutor v Tadic*, Case No. IT-94-1-AR72, Appeals Chamber, Decision on the Defence Motion for Interlocutory Appeal on Jurisdiction, 2 October 1995

²⁶ *Ibid*, 562

but it is unnecessary to demonstrate that the rebel group is in control of the territory.²⁷ Yet it may be difficult to show that a conflict is characterised by a high degree of violence and this, for example, averts that Protocol II applies to NIACs, which just start. Equally, demonstrating that the rebel group is organised may prove challenging.

Moreover, in *Tadic* a possible further condition of “protracted hostilities” was identified in order to establish that there is an armed conflict, but this is debated.²⁸ A very high threshold was established by the Report of the International Commission of Inquiry on Darfur to the UNS-G 2005, which required for a NIAC to be made out that organised groups fight the state; organised groups control some areas; and that fighting is protracted.²⁹ This is problematic, also because the conceptual distinction between IACs and NIACs has become more and more obsolete post 9/11, where many armed conflicts take place between non-state organisations and states within a transnational context.³⁰

As there are different forms of NIACs (for instance, those where only CA3 apply; where additionally Protocol 2 applies; where the ICC Statute, Article 8(2)(e) applies together with CA3; or instances where the conflict is not against the state; or the conflict has become internationalised), civilians would be better protected if it was only required that the fighting has a particular intensity and happens for a certain duration.³¹

1.1.2 Combatants/fighters

²⁷ N.17 (Sivakumaran) 165

²⁸ *Prosecutor v Tadic*, Case No. IT-94-1-AR72, Appeals Chamber, Decision on the Defence Motion for Interlocutory Appeal on Jurisdiction, 2 October 1995, para.70; E. Wilmshurst, *International Law and the Classification of Conflicts* (Oxford, Oxford University Press 2012) 51

²⁹ A. Kaczorowska, *Public International* (4th ed, Abingdon, Routledge 2010) 823

³⁰ C. Kreß, *The Treatment of Combatants and Insurgents under the Law of Armed Conflict* By Emily Crawford, *The Concept of NIAC in International Humanitarian Law*. By Anthony Cullen, *Extraterritorial Use of Force Against Non-State Actors*. By Noam Lubell, *The Law of NIAC*. By Sandesh Sivakumaran, 83(1) *British Yearbook of International Law* 2012, 145, 145

³¹ M. E. O'Connell, *What Is War?: An Investigation in the Wake of 9/11* (Leiden, Koninklijke 2012) 29

Those, who fight for the state military are considered combatants, whereas those who fight for dissident or rebel groups, including civilians, are labeled fighters.³² Yet it is difficult to determine where status based targeting starts, what constitutes membership of an organised armed group and to differentiate between direct partaking in hostilities and continuous combat function.³³ This is problematic because civilians may be mistaken for fighters and fighters are not afforded any privileges and rights by CA3 or Protocol II.³⁴

1.1.3 Specially protected persons

Problems also exist when it comes to protecting specially protected persons during NIACs. Whilst protected persons are defined for IACs,³⁵ CA3 omits a definition for “protected persons.”³⁶ However, the way in which protected persons are defined in respect of IACs is inappropriate for NIACs.³⁷ Consequently, only certain basic protections are granted to the sick and wounded, including children³⁸ and persons whose liberty has been limited.³⁹ Sex and race discrimination are proscribed.⁴⁰

Protocol II stresses that humane treatment is essential and thus sets out fundamental guarantees, for instance, to revere the religious customs of all those, who do not directly

³² Article 1(1) of AP 2; J.-M. Henckaerts, L. Doswald-Beck, *Customary International Humanitarian Law, Volume I: Rules* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press 2005) 13

³³ N. Melzer, *Interpretive Guidance on the Notion of Direct Participation in Hostilities under International Humanitarian Law*, International Committee of the Red Cross, 2009, 1, 12
<<https://www.icrc.org/eng/assets/files/other/icrc-002-0990.pdf>> accessed 10th September 2015

³⁴ E. Crawford, *The Treatment of Combatants and Insurgents Under the Law of Armed Conflict* (Oxford, Oxford University Press 2010) 3; J.-M. Henckaerts, L. Doswald-Beck, *Customary International Humanitarian Law, Volume 2: Practice* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press 2005) 82

³⁵ Article 4 of Convention IV

³⁶ F. Kalshoven, L. Zegveld, *Constraints on the Waging of War: An Introduction to International Humanitarian Law* (4th ed, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press 2011) 46

³⁷ M. Matthee, B. Toebe, M. Brus, *Armed Conflict and International Law: In Search of the Human Face: Liber Amicorum in Memory of Avril McDonald* (The Hague, TMC Asser Press 2013) 292; S. Weill, *The Role of National Courts in Applying International Humanitarian Law* (Oxford, Oxford University Press 2014) 53

³⁸ Article 4 of Protocol II

³⁹ Articles 5&7 of Protocol II

⁴⁰ Article 2 of Protocol II

participate.⁴¹ Eight acts, such as terrorism, slavery and pillage, are outlawed against all those who participate or no longer directly partake in the fighting.⁴² The sick, shipwrecked, wounded or dead have to be searched for and protected and cared for without undue delay.⁴³ Yet customary international law additionally requires that all possible steps have to be taken to account for missing persons and to furnish information to their families, but this is not mentioned in Protocol II.⁴⁴

Religious and medical personnel are afforded protection,⁴⁵ though they have to display a distinctive emblem.⁴⁶ Customary international law requires that women are afforded additional rights and protections,⁴⁷ but Protocol II does not contain these.⁴⁸ Instead, Protocol II only requires that pregnant women are not sentenced to death or mothers with young children.⁴⁹ Similarly, journalists,⁵⁰ the infirm, disabled and elderly should be afforded special protection, but Protocol II fails to do this.⁵¹ Also, the scope of protection for children is more expansive in Protocol I. Protocol II only requires that children are cared for and receive aid, especially education; efforts are made to reunite them with their families; they are not recruited to participate in the hostilities if they are not yet fifteen years of age; and if they have nevertheless joined fighting, they are nonetheless afforded these protective safeguards; and steps have to be taken to move them away from areas where fighting takes place.⁵² Those, who are below the age of eighteen, cannot be sentenced to death.⁵³

⁴¹ Article 4 of Protocol II

⁴² Article 4 (2)(a)-(h) of Protocol II

⁴³ Articles 7-8 of Protocol II

⁴⁴ N.11 (Bouchet-Saulnier et al) 409

⁴⁵ Articles 9-11 of Protocol II

⁴⁶ Article 12 of Protocol II

⁴⁷ Also see Article 76 of Protocol I

⁴⁸ International Committee of the Red Cross, Rule 134, Women, 2015 <https://www.icrc.org/customary-ihl/eng/docs/v1_cha_chapter39_rule134> accessed 25th May 2015

⁴⁹ Article 6(4) of Protocol II

⁵⁰ Also see Articles 69&79 of Protocol I

⁵¹ N.11 (Bouchet-Saulnier et al) 529

⁵² Article 4(3) of Protocol II

⁵³ Article 6(4) of Protocol II

Persons cannot be internally displaced, except when there are ample military reasons or this is necessary to safeguard their security and civilians should not be forced to move because of the hostilities.⁵⁴ In case they are internally displaced, steps should be taken to provide adequate shelter, health facilities, food, hygiene, safety and nutrition, though this obligation does not apply if they voluntarily leave to escape the hostilities.⁵⁵ An analysis of the provisions in the Convention IV and Protocol I shows that the law regulating internal displacement during NIACs is not as detailed. Yet internal conflicts often result in internal displacement.⁵⁶

Furthermore, Protocol II does not contain any provisions dealing with refugees, despite the fact that “non-refoulement of refugees” is treated as part of customary law.⁵⁷ Equally, no mention is made that UN peacekeepers and associated personnel are protected, despite international law mandating this.⁵⁸

1.1.4 Civilians

The term 'civilians' is not defined by CA3 and Protocol II, though CA3 affords minimum guarantees, such as humane treatment, violence against the person and discrimination and Protocol II makes clear that civilians have to be safeguarded.⁵⁹ In IACs, a negative definition is adopted⁶⁰ and those who are non-combatants are civilians i.e. those, who do not directly partake in the hostilities for the time.⁶¹ No safeguards are afforded to

⁵⁴ Article 17(1)-(2) of Protocol II

⁵⁵ Article 17(1) of Protocol II

⁵⁶ N.4 (Phuong) 45

⁵⁷ Also see the Convention relating to the Status of Refugees 1951; M. R. Islam, J. H. Bhuiyan, *An Introduction to International Refugee Law* (Leiden, Koninklijke Brill NV 2013) 169

⁵⁸ Convention on the Safety of United Nations and Associated Personnel 1994; n.17 (Sivakumaran) 327

⁵⁹ Article 13 of Protocol II; n.32 (Henckaerts and Doswald-Beck) 19; N. Burri, *Bravery or Bravado? The Protection of News Providers in Armed Conflict* (Leiden, Koninklijke Brill NV 2015) 133

⁶⁰ A. Van Engeland, *Civilian or Combatant?: A Challenge for the 21st Century* (Oxford, Oxford University Press 2011) 29

⁶¹ Article 50 of Protocol I

those, who participate and these can be prosecuted for war crimes.⁶² It is presumed that a person is a civilian when this is uncertain.⁶³

Article 13(3) of Protocol II qualifies the protection and civilians are only protected so long as they do not directly partake. However, this is problematic since practically this means that a combatant/fighter has to determine whether or not a person should be considered a civilian or combatant. A fighter may not work full-time and this blurs the distinction between civilian and combatant.⁶⁴ It also makes it easy for civilians to lose their immunity from attack in a NIAC.⁶⁵ Also, security and military contractors, intelligence and civilian employees, who may undertake important “military” acts, are considered civilians, rather than combatants/fighters.⁶⁶ However, it is unclear whether this is the case when, e.g., the secret service use drones, as for example, has happened in the NIACs in Afghanistan and Pakistan.⁶⁷ The absence of an effective legal regime to govern drone strikes puts the lives of civilians at risk.⁶⁸

The way in which the term “take a direct part in hostilities”⁶⁹ is described is very similar in NIACs and IACs.⁷⁰ However, the Geneva Conventions and Protocols do not inform how the term should be interpreted and whilst the ICRC has provided guidance, this omission has

⁶² R. Arnold, ‘The liability of civilians under international humanitarian law's war crimes provisions’ in (eds) H. Fischer, A. McDonald, *Yearbook of International Humanitarian Law - 2002* (The Hague, TMC Asser Instituut 2005) 356

⁶³ Article 50(1) of the API; Y. Arai, *The Law of Occupation: Continuity and Change of International Humanitarian Law, and its Interaction with International Human Rights Law* (Leiden, Koninklijke Brill NV 2009) 308

⁶⁴ N.3 (Perna) 64

⁶⁵ N.33 (Melzer) 16

⁶⁶ I. Wilson, J. J. F. Forest, *Handbook of Defence Politics: International and Comparative Perspectives* (Abingdon, Routledge 2011) 110; n.33 (Melzer) 38

⁶⁷ A. C. Orr, Unmanned, Unprecedented, and Unresolved: The Status of American Drone Strikes in Pakistan Under International Law, 44 *Cornell International Law Journal* 2011, 729, 733

⁶⁸ I. Henderson, Civilian Intelligence Agencies and the Use of Armed Drones, 13 *Yearbook of International Humanitarian Law* 2011, 133-173, 133; *ibid* (Orr) 733

⁶⁹ Article 51(3) of Protocol I

⁷⁰ Article 13(3) of Protocol II; CA3; M. Bothe, Direct Participation in Hostilities in Non-International Armed Conflicts, Second Expert Meeting on the Notion of Direct Participation in Hostilities, The Hague, 25/26 October 2004, 1-18, 18 <<https://www.icrc.org/eng/assets/files/other/2004-05-expert-paper-dph-icrc.pdf>> accessed 20th May 2015

nonetheless created legal uncertainty and ambiguity.⁷¹ Despite the ICRC guidance, practical application is difficult.⁷² For instance, should those, who help with the logistics for those, who take part or gather intelligence, be treated as combatants/fighters or civilians?⁷³ Also, how should it be determined where status based targeting begins and whether this is based on the CA3 or Protocol II threshold?⁷⁴

Furthermore, civilians are unprotected since rebel groups are not required to wear markings or uniforms to identify themselves as combatants and the state military may therefore accidentally target civilians, particularly if the civilians had guns to protect themselves.⁷⁵ As a corollary, distinguishing combatants/fighters from civilians is rather difficult.

1.2 Fundamental IHL principles

Civilians are also protected by important IHL principles which regulate the conduct of war.⁷⁶

Yet these do not provide absolute protection for civilians.

1.2.1 Limitation

⁷¹ D. Fleck, *The Handbook of International Humanitarian Law* (Oxford, Oxford University Press 2013) 255; D. Akande, Clearing the Fog of War? The ICRC's Interpretive Guidance on Direct Participation in Hostilities, Blog of the European Journal of International Law, 4 June 2009 <<http://www.ejiltalk.org/clearing-the-fog-of-war-the-icrcs-interpretive-guidance-on-direct-participation-in-hostilities/>> accessed 17th May 2015

⁷² Ibid

⁷³ Ibid

⁷⁴ N. Melzer, Keeping the Balance Between Military Necessity and Humanity, A Response to Four Critiques of the ICRC's Interpretive Guidance on the Notion of Direct Participation in Hostilities, 42 *International Law and Politics* 2010, 833, 857; M. N. Schmitt, Deconstructing Direct Participation in Hostilities: The Constitutive Elements, 42 *New York University Journal of International Law and Politics* 2010, 697, 720; B. Boothby, "And for such time as": The Time Dimension to Direct Participation in Hostilities, 42 *New York University Journal of International Law & Politics* 2010, 741, 768

⁷⁵ N.15 (Dinstein) 214

⁷⁶ International Committee of the Red Cross, Practice Relating to Rule 1, The Principle of Distinction between Civilians and Combatants, 2015 <https://www.icrc.org/customary-ihl/eng/docs/v2_rul_rule1> accessed 17th May 2015

The principle of limitation was first affirmed in 1874.⁷⁷ The principle denies the possibility to engage in total war in order to win an armed dispute; thereby limiting the means and methods of warfare.⁷⁸ The principle also limits the principle of military necessity.⁷⁹ For effective civilian protection, this principle should limit the weapons which can be used, as well as the trade in arms, in accordance with international law.⁸⁰ However, CA3 and Protocol II are silent in respect of weapons and this is only regulated by customary law.⁸¹

1.2.2 Military necessity

Military necessity dates back to Articles 14-16 of the Lieber Code 1863.⁸² The ICJ has affirmed that IHL “contains provisions enabling account to be taken of military exigencies in certain circumstances.”⁸³ It has been affirmed as a defence,⁸⁴ but not in respect of targeting civilians.⁸⁵ The principle denotes taking those steps which are necessary to secure

⁷⁷ See the Project of an International Declaration Concerning the Laws and Customs of War 1874; also see Article 22 of the Hague Convention (II) With Respect to the Laws and Customs of War on Land 1899, in Article 22 of the Fourth Hague Convention 1907 and in Article 35(1) of Protocol I; K. Hulme, *War Torn Environment: Interpreting The Legal Threshold* (Leiden, Koninklijke Brill NV 2004) 118-119

⁷⁸ R. Kolb, *Advanced Introduction to International Humanitarian Law* (Cheltenham, Edward Elgar Publishing Ltd 2014) 80

⁷⁹ Ibid (Kolb)

⁸⁰ Article 35 of Protocol I, the Ottawa Treaty 1997; the Convention on Cluster Munitions 2008; the Biological Weapons Conventions 1972; the Chemical Weapons Convention 1993; the Convention on Certain Conventional Weapons 1980; the Arms Trade Treaty 2013; Diakonia, *Weapons and International Humanitarian Law*, 11 December 2013 <<https://www.diakonia.se/en/IHL/The-Law/International-Humanitarian-Law-1/Issues-addressed-by-IHL/Conduct-of-Hostilities/Weapons/>> accessed 7th September 2015

⁸¹ N.77 (Hulme) 218

⁸² Also see the St Petersburg Declaration 1868; G. D. Solis, *The Law of Armed Conflict: International Humanitarian Law in War* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press 2010) 258; M. N. Schmitt, *Essays on Law and War at the Fault Lines* (The Hague, TMC Asser Press 2012) 94; C. A. Ford, A. Cohen, *Rethinking the Law of Armed Conflict in an Age of Terrorism* (Plymouth, Lexington Books 2012) 202

⁸³ *Legal Consequences of the Construction of a Wall in the Occupied Palestinian Territory*, Advisory Opinion [2004] I.C.J. Rep., p.106, para.135; cited from S. Darcy, *Judges, Law and War: The Judicial Development of International Humanitarian Law* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press 2014) 146

⁸⁴ Articles 2(d) and 3(b) Statute of the International Criminal Tribunal for the former Yugoslavia 1992; W. Schabas, *The International Criminal Court: A Commentary on the Rome Statute* (Oxford, Oxford University Press 2010) 496

⁸⁵ *Prosecutor v Blaskic*, Case No. IT-95-14-T, Judgment, 3 March 2000, paras.180, 651; *Kordic et al* (IT-95-14/2-T), Judgment, 26 February 2001, para.328; *Prosecutor v Rajic*, Case No. T-95-12-R61, Review of the Indictment Pursuant to Rule 61 of the Rules of Procedure and Evidence, 13 September 1996, paras54-57; *Kordic et al* (IT-95-14/2-1), Judgment, 17 December 2004, para.54; *Prosecutor v Blaskic*, Case No. IT-95-14-A, Judgment, 29 July 2004, para.109; *ibid* (Schabas) 496

that the war ends and which comply with the methods of warfare.⁸⁶ However, it not only allows that enemies are killed, but also other persons, whose “destruction is incidentally unavoidable”.⁸⁷ Yet cruelty i.e. causing suffering for revenge or for the sake of it is not permitted, nor acts which make it difficult to restore peace.⁸⁸ Hence, the principle ensures that no more use of force is used as is required to realise complete or partial submission of the opponent.⁸⁹ This implies a “proportionality calculus” i.e. that humanity and military necessity are balanced against each other.⁹⁰ For example, a civilian object, which is an unlawful target, can be attacked if this is necessary to achieve submission of the opponent.⁹¹ Yet the issue is if not equal weight is attached to considerations of humanity, this principle can result in an “extremely permissive targeting regime prone to an unacceptable degree of error and arbitrariness.”⁹²

1.2.3 Proportionality

The principle of proportionality is another important qualifier for the use of force.⁹³ The ICRC considers proportionality a customary principle in respect of NIACs.⁹⁴ Such an approach is preferred, particularly since the principle is not mentioned in Protocol II and can only be indirectly implied through the principle of humanity mentioned in the preamble.⁹⁵ As

⁸⁶ Article 14 of the Lieber Code 1863

⁸⁷ Article 15 of the Lieber Code 1863

⁸⁸ Article 16 of the Lieber Code 1863

⁸⁹ N.82 (Ford and Cohen) 202

⁹⁰ M. N. Schmitt, L. Arimatsu, T. McCormack, *Yearbook of International Humanitarian Law - 2010* (The Hague, TMC Asser Instituut 2011) 231

⁹¹ Cf *Prosecutor v Galic*, Case No. IT-98-29-T, 5 December 2003; n.82 (Solis) 253 ; I. Henderson, *The Contemporary Law of Targeting, Military Objectives, Proportionality and Precautions in Attack under Additional Protocol I* (Leiden, Koninklijke Brill NV 2009) 44

⁹² N.74 (Melzer) 913

⁹³ N.32 (Henckaerts and Doswald-Beck) 48

⁹⁴ See Rule 14, International Committee of the Red Cross Study, Vol. I; *ibid* (Henckaerts and Doswald-Beck) 46-49; also see Article 3(8)(c) of the Amended Protocol II to the Convention on Certain Conventional Weapons; cited from A. Müller, *The Relationship between Economic, Social and Cultural Rights and International Humanitarian Law* (Leiden, Koninklijke Brill NV 2013) 59; n.32 (Henckaerts and Doswald-Beck) 48

⁹⁵ *Ibid* (Henckaerts and Doswald-Beck) 48

explicated by the ICJ⁹⁶, “even a legitimate target may not be attacked if the collateral civilian casualties would be disproportionate to the specific military gain from the attack” and the same is the case in respect of damaging civilian property.⁹⁷ Hence, the principle further limits force since ‘excessive’ collateral damage (i.e. injuring civilians or damaging civilian objects) is proscribed.⁹⁸ The issue is that it is easy to pay lip-service since it encapsulates a relative concept, which requires a comparison in light of the “overall” anticipated military benefits.⁹⁹

1.2.4 Distinction

The IHL principle of distinction is very important and can be traced back to the United States (US) civil war in which it was tacitly affirmed.¹⁰⁰ Yet before the Additional Protocols in 1977, only some texts referred to it in relation to causing damage to civilian infrastructure.¹⁰¹ Yet it had not matured since civilian losses were perceived an unavoidable consequence of war.¹⁰² The principle safeguards civilians because it mandates that civilians are distinguished from combatants/fighters.¹⁰³ Distinction has been affirmed by various treaties¹⁰⁴ and in other instruments,¹⁰⁵ in military manuals¹⁰⁶ and by domestic case law.¹⁰⁷

⁹⁶ *Legality of the Threat or Use of Nuclear Weapons*, Advisory Opinion [1996] I.C.J. Rep., p.226, Dissenting Opinion by Judge R. Higgins

⁹⁷ Cited from K. M. Larsen, C. G. Cooper, G. Nystuen, *Searching for a 'Principle of Humanity' in International Humanitarian Law* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press 2012) 75

⁹⁸ Ibid (Larsen et al) 75

⁹⁹ Article 8(2)(b)(iv) of the Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court 1998 (Rome Statute); n.97 (Larsen et al) 76

¹⁰⁰ Lieber Code 1863; H. Olásolo, *Unlawful Attacks in Combat Situations: From the ICCTY's Case Law to the Rome Statute* (Leiden, Koninklijke Brill NV 2008) 15

¹⁰¹ See Brussels Declaration 1874; Article 27 Regulations Annexed to the Hague Convention (IV) respecting the Laws and Customs of War on Land and its annex: Regulations concerning the Laws and Customs of War on Land. The Hague, 18 October 1907

¹⁰² N.100 (Olásolo) 15

¹⁰³ N.76 (International Committee of the Red Cross)

¹⁰⁴ Also see Article 48 of Protocol I; preamble of the Ottawa Convention on Anti-Personnel Mines 1997; preamble of the Convention on Cluster Munitions 2008

¹⁰⁵ See para.2(5) of the Agreement on the Application of IHL between the Parties to the Conflict in Bosnia and Herzegovina 1992

¹⁰⁶ See Belgium's Law of War Manual 1983

Civilians and civilian objects cannot be attacked.¹⁰⁸ The principle is implicitly affirmed by the Geneva Conventions, which spell out who should be considered a protected person.¹⁰⁹ Protocol I, Article 48 expressly includes this principle.¹¹⁰ It forms part of the essential IHL principles, the other ones being the proscription “to cause unnecessary suffering to combatants”, as well as the Martens Clause which are “intransgressible [within]...international customary law” and which are directly derived from “elementary considerations of humanity.”¹¹¹ The International Law Commission notes that this principle amounts to a *jus cogens*.¹¹² It is thus a customary rule, which has to be followed during NIACs.¹¹³

1.2.5 Good faith

Another principle is that of good faith, which constitutes another fundamental customary international law rule and necessitates that the rules are honestly applied to armed conflicts and that negotiations are conducted with sincerity.¹¹⁴

1.3 Issues affecting the protection of civilians during armed conflicts

¹⁰⁷ See the Israeli case of *Physicians for Human Rights v Prime Minister of Israel* 2009; n.76 (International Committee of the Red Cross)

¹⁰⁸ T. McCormack, A. McDonald, *Yearbook of International Humanitarian Law - 2003* (The Hague, TMC Asser Press 2006) 6

¹⁰⁹ N.82 (Schmitt) 177

¹¹⁰ N.32 (Henckaerts and Doswald-Beck) 4

¹¹¹ *Legality of the Threat or Use of Nuclear Weapons*, Advisory Opinion [1996] I.C.J. Rep., p.226, para.78; cited from A. Clapham, P. Gaeta, *The Oxford Handbook of International Law in Armed Conflict* (Oxford, Oxford University Press 2014) 297

¹¹² International Law Commission, Report on State Responsibility, *Yearbook of the International Law Commission, 2001*, Volume II, Part Two, Draft Article 40, Commentary, 112; *ibid* (Clapham and Gaeta) 297

¹¹³ *Prosecutor v Tadic*, Case No. IT-94-1-AR72, Appeals Chamber, Decision on the Defence Motion for Interlocutory Appeal on Jurisdiction, 2 October 1995, paras.111-112; J. Crowe, K. Weston-Scheuber, *Principles of International Humanitarian Law* (Cheltenham, Edward Elgar Publishing Ltd 2013) 80

¹¹⁴ International Committee of the Red Cross, *The Law of Armed Conflict, Basic knowledge*, June 2002, 1-29, 14 <https://www.icrc.org/eng/assets/files/other/law1_final.pdf> accessed 29th May 2015

As mentioned, since 1945, the great majority of armed conflicts have been of an internal nature.¹¹⁵ The adoption of Protocol II is particularly important to broaden the protective reach for civilians and to address the deficiencies of CA3, thereby “putting flesh on the bare bones of CA3.”¹¹⁶ Yet an analysis of the protective safeguards contained in Protocol II demonstrates that they are not analogous to those contained in Protocol I. For instance, Part III of Protocol I spells out detailed rules about the methods and means of warfare, whereas no such provisions can be found in Protocol II. Also, Protocol I has more than 80 articles, whereas there are only 15 contained in Protocol II.¹¹⁷

Furthermore, Protocol II omits to address several essential matters, for instance, no mention is made that grave violations should result in criminal liability.¹¹⁸ In contrast, Geneva Convention IV is like “a bill of rights [for civilians] with a catalogue of fundamental rights...”¹¹⁹ Yet the manner in which the safeguards are worded in Protocol II is much less expansive.¹²⁰ Resultantly, there are not as many protections available for civilians during NIACs not only because Protocol II has not as many treaty provisions, but also since the few are rudimentary.

Furthermore, the safeguards in Geneva Conventions III¹²¹ and IV (apart from CA3) do not apply to NIACs and equally analogous customary law may not apply during NIACs.¹²²

¹¹⁵ N.57 (Islam and Bhuiyan) 165

¹¹⁶ C. Greenwood, ‘Critique of the Additional Protocols to the Geneva conventions’ in (eds) H. Durham, T. L. H. McCormack, A. Gilbert, Alan, *The Changing Face of Conflict and the Efficacy of International Humanitarian Law. International humanitarian law, Vol. 1(2)* (Leiden, Martinus Nijhoff Publishers) 3-22, 14; cited from n.12 (Cullen) 87

¹¹⁷ J.-M. Henckaerts, Study on customary international humanitarian law: A contribution to the understanding and respect for the rule of law in armed conflict, 87(857) *International Review of the Red Cross* 2005, 175, 178

¹¹⁸ L. A. Horvitz, C. Catherwood, *Encyclopedia of War Crimes and Genocide* (New York, Facts on File Inc 2006) 462

¹¹⁹ H. P. Gasser, ‘Protection of the Civilian Population’, in (eds) n.71 (Fleck) 242; cited from 180

¹²⁰ L. Cameron, V. Chetail, *Privatizing War: Private Military and Security Companies under Public International Law* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press 2013) 423

¹²¹ Convention (III) relative to the Treatment of Prisoners of War. Geneva, 12 August 1949 (Convention III)

1.4 Civilian protection through CA3 and Protocol II and customary IHL

The detailed provisions in Convention IV¹²³ and the provisions dealing with civilian protections in Protocol I do not apply in respect of NIACs. Instead, civilian protection is assured by virtue of CA3, which is “a minimum yardstick” of customary international law.¹²⁴ It sets out a wide obligation and thereby safeguards humanity by outlawing certain acts¹²⁵ and imposes a particular duty to collect and care for the wounded and sick.¹²⁶ Yet the Article is not specific enough and many important aspects to protect civilians have not been addressed, though Protocol II “develops and supplements CA3.”¹²⁷

The objective of Protocol II is to facilitate “respect for the human person” and basic protection in accordance with human rights instruments, so that better victim protection is realised in accordance with “the principles of humanity...[and] public conscience.”¹²⁸ This latter formulation is a so-called Martens clause.¹²⁹ Common ideals become included as customary international law, irrespective of whether a state abrogates the treaty.¹³⁰ Yet the wording of Protocol II’s clause is more restrictive than the one in Protocol I because it omits to mention customary international and international law.¹³¹

¹²² M. N. Schmitt, *Tallinn Manual on the International Law Applicable to Cyber Warfare* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press 2013) 214

¹²³ Article 3 Convention IV

¹²⁴ *Prosecutor v Delalic et al*, Case No. IT-96-21-A, 20 February 2001, para.143; n.82 (Solis) 99

¹²⁵ CA3(1)(a)-(d)

¹²⁶ CA3(2)

¹²⁷ N.15 (Jinks et al) 37

¹²⁸ Preamble of Protocol II

¹²⁹ G. Oberleitner, *Human Rights in Armed Conflict, Law, Practice, Policy* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press 2015) 33&35

¹³⁰ *Ibid*

¹³¹ T. Meron, The Martens Clause, Principles of Humanity, and Dictates of Public Conscience, 94(1) *American Journal of International Law* 2000, 78, 80

Certainly, civilian protection is mandated by Protocol II,¹³² but it omits to mention the principle of distinction. However, as discussed above, this principle forms part of customary law and resultantly so-called “Hague or battlefield law” applies.¹³³ An analysis of the equivalent provision in Protocol I¹³⁴ shows that this provision is much more expansive than in Protocol II.

Nonetheless, objects, which are indispensable to the survival of the civilian population,¹³⁵ as well as works and installations containing dangerous forces,¹³⁶ and cultural objects and places of worship,¹³⁷ are protected. Forced movement of civilians is prohibited.¹³⁸ Yet in respect of affording relief, the language of Protocol II is less prescriptive and rather general and states that relief societies “may offer their services...”¹³⁹ Consent has to be obtained even in situations where civilians experience undue hardship before relief can be provided.¹⁴⁰ This reflects that relief is frequently perceived as “foreign assistance to rebellion.”¹⁴¹ However, a failure to consent breaches Article 14 of Protocol II when impartial relief is offered in circumstances where the population may otherwise suffer from starvation.¹⁴²

Customary IHL has emerged, which also applies to NIACs, thereby extending the protective safeguards for civilians to a certain extent. This development has been particularly

¹³² Article 13 of Protocol II

¹³³ Cited from F. Kalshoven, *Reflections on the Law of War: Collected Essays* (Leiden, Koninklijke Brill NV 2007) ix

¹³⁴ Article 51 of Protocol II

¹³⁵ Article 14 of Protocol II

¹³⁶ Article 15 of Protocol II

¹³⁷ Article 16 of Protocol II

¹³⁸ Article 17 of Protocol II

¹³⁹ Article 18(1) of Protocol II

¹⁴⁰ Article 18(2) of Protocol II

¹⁴¹ M. Bothe, K. J. Partsch, W. A. Solf, *New Rules for Victims of Armed Conflicts: Commentary on the Two 1977 Protocols Additional to the Geneva Conventions of 1949* (2nd ed, Leiden, Koninklijke Brill NV 2013) 799

¹⁴² A.-K. Lindblom, *Non-Governmental Organisations in International Law* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press 2005) 215

driven by the *Tadic* case,¹⁴³ in which it was found that particular customary international rules apply to NIAC and that “[t]his holds true for common Article 3...[and] Article 19 of the Hague Convention for the Protection of Cultural Property in the Event of Armed Conflicts...1954 and...to the core of Additional Protocol II...”¹⁴⁴ Also, a breach of these provisions can result in the imposition of criminal responsibility for perpetrators.¹⁴⁵ The ICJ has made clear that common Article 3 reflects “elementary considerations of humanity.”¹⁴⁶ Furthermore, Article 8(2)(3) of the Rome Statute includes many “violations of the laws and customs applicable in armed conflicts not of an international character” and includes forcibly compelling the conscription or enlisting of those below 15 years¹⁴⁷ and rape.¹⁴⁸ Customary international law has thereby been progressively developed by granting jurisdiction to the ICC in respect of these matters.¹⁴⁹

Nonetheless, as pointed out by Judge Jennings,¹⁵⁰ it is very difficult to distil the relevant state practice, which is a required prerequisite together with the *opinio juris*, in order to demonstrate that, for example, a particular provision contained in a treaty amounts to customary international law.¹⁵¹ Hence, in respect of each treaty provision, it has to be analysed whether this represents custom.¹⁵² As not all rules which govern IACs can be

¹⁴³ *Prosecutor v Tadic*, Case No. IT-94-1-AR72, Appeals Chamber, Decision on the Defence Motion for Interlocutory Appeal on Jurisdiction, 2 October 1995

¹⁴⁴ *Ibid.*, 62-67; cited from Human Rights Watch, *Justice in the Balance: Recommendations for an Independent and Effective International Criminal Court* (London, Human Rights Watch 1998) 23

¹⁴⁵ *Ibid.*, paras 96-137; R. O’Keefe, *International Criminal Law* (Oxford, Oxford University Press 2015) 126

¹⁴⁶ *Military and Paramilitary Activities in and against Nicaragua (Nicaragua v United States of America)* [1986] I.C.J. Rep., p.14, para.218; V. Chetail, The contribution of the International Court of Justice to international humanitarian law, 85(850) *International Review of the Red Cross* 2003, 235, 245

¹⁴⁷ Article 8(2)(vii) of the Rome Statute

¹⁴⁸ Article 8(2)(e)(vi) of the Rome Statute; n.145 (O’Keefe) 127

¹⁴⁹ *Ibid.* (O’Keefe)

¹⁵⁰ *Military and Paramilitary Activities In and Against Nicaragua (Nicaragua v United States of America)* [1986] I.C.J. Rep., p.14

¹⁵¹ *Ibid.*, 531 (Dissenting Opinion by Judge Sir Robert Jennings); Y. Arai, *Continuity and Change of International Humanitarian Law, and its Interaction with International Human Rights Law* (Leiden, Koninklijke Brill NV 2009) 627

¹⁵² N.15 (Dinstein) 10

transposed to the context of NIACs, only those provisions in Protocol II, which are derived from CA3, can be considered customary international law.¹⁵³

Moreover, Meron has contended that since all core rights set out in the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) are contained in Protocol II, and several of these human rights constitute customary international law, that Protocol II should remain to have customary force.¹⁵⁴ Certainly, IHL can be depicted “as the human rights law of armed conflict”, but whilst IHL and IHR have shared values, their histories are different, there is a conceptual gap between the two regimes (IHL deals with the relationship between individuals and the state, whereas IHR regulates the relationship between two states and/or armed groups) and the substance is different.¹⁵⁵ As also discussed, *opinio juris* and state practice are required and treaty law is relevant, and it is therefore difficult to argue that all Articles in Protocol II amount to customary international law.¹⁵⁶ Furthermore, out of the 196 countries in the world, 166 have ratified Protocol II, but many of those with internal conflicts have not ratified the Protocol.¹⁵⁷

1.5 Summary

It has been shown that the rules governing NIACs are less developed than those which govern IACs. As a result, civilians often bear the brunt of internal wars. Yet civilians are also afforded protection through IHR which is examined in the next chapter.

¹⁵³ B. Schlütter, *Developments in Customary International Law: Theory and the Practice of the International Court of Justice and the International Ad Hoc Criminal Tribunals for Rwanda and Yugoslavia* (Leiden, Martinus Nijhoff Publishers 2010) 243-244

¹⁵⁴ T. Meron, *Human Rights and Humanitarian Norms as Customary Law* (Oxford, Clarendon Press 1989) 73; L. Moir, *The Law of Internal Armed Conflict* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press 2004) 133

¹⁵⁵ D. Moeckli, S. Shah, S. Sivakumaran, D. Harris, *International Human Rights Law* (Oxford, Oxford University Press 2014) 480-482

¹⁵⁶ N.117 (Henckaerts182&188

¹⁵⁷ P. Ambach, F. Bostedt, G. Dawson, S. Kostas, *The Protection of Non-Combatants During Armed Conflict and Safeguarding the Rights of Victims in Post-Conflict Society* (Leiden, Koninklijke Brill NV 2015) 79

Chapter 2: Extending the protective reach for civilians through IHR in NIACs

1.0 Introduction

Important IHR standards have been affirmed, for instance, in the UDHR, the ICCPR, the ICESCR, as well as by regional human rights treaties, such as the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR) 1950. This chapter analyses to what extent these IHR standards protect civilians during NIACs.

2.1 Important IHR values

Like IHL, IHR law is concerned with safeguarding human life.¹⁵⁸ The UDHR, the ICCPR, the ICESCR, as well as regional human rights treaties¹⁵⁹ spell out important IHR values, though human rights have also been affirmed in treaties.¹⁶⁰ The UNSC, the UN General Assembly (UNGA) and the Human Rights Council have issued resolutions, the UN human rights treaty bodies have published decisions, UN special rapporteurs have investigated human rights issues and have made suggestions about how to address them and courts have

¹⁵⁸ *Abella (La Tablada) Case, Argentina* (18 November 1997) Case 11.137, Report No. 55/97, Inter-American Commission on Human Rights, para.19;

¹⁵⁹ For instance, see the American Convention on Human Rights 1969 (ACHR) and the European Convention on Human Rights 1950 (ECHR)

¹⁶⁰ For instance, see the Convention against Torture and other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment 1984

reached findings.¹⁶¹ Resultantly, there are different sources of IHR law, but the issue is that this results in “conflicts between rules or rule-systems, deviating institutional practices and loss of an overall perspective on the law.”¹⁶² Moreover, it is uncertain which human rights represent customary international law rules which protect civilians.¹⁶³

The ICJ has pointed out that “the protection offered by human rights conventions does not cease in case of armed conflict, save for the effect of provisions for derogation...”¹⁶⁴ IHRs thus act as an additional restraining force during NIACs, as confirmed in the Advisory Opinion on *the Legality of the Threat or Use of Nuclear Weapons*¹⁶⁵ where it was noted that “[i]n principle, the right not arbitrarily to be deprived of one's life applies also in hostilities...”¹⁶⁶

Accordingly, states are required to observe human rights and therefore adopt enforcement mechanisms in order to investigate, prosecute and punish offenders and compensate victims the state or non-state actors violate their duties.¹⁶⁷ However, it would be wrong to assume that during NIACs civilians are entitled to the entire range of human rights spelled out in IHR treaties, especially progressive cultural, social and economic human rights since states find it difficult to provide these even during times of peace.¹⁶⁸

¹⁶¹ B. G. Ramcharan, *The Law, Policy and Politics of the UN Human Rights Council* (Leiden, Koninklijke Brill NV 2015) 76

¹⁶² UN General Assembly, International Law Commission, Fragmentation of International Law: Difficulties Arising from the Diversification and Expansion of International Law: Report of the Study Group of the International Law Commission, finalised by Martti Koskenniemi, UN Doc.A/CN.4/L.682 (2006), para.14; cited from S. Sheeran, N. Rodley, *Routledge Handbook of International Human Rights Law* (Abingdon, Routledge 2013) 515

¹⁶³ N.17 (Sivakumaran) 55

¹⁶⁴ *Legal Consequences of the Construction of a Wall in the Occupied Palestinian Territory*, Advisory Opinion [2004] I.C.J. Rep., p.106, p.178, paras102-106; cited from O. Ben-Naftali, *International Humanitarian Law and International Human Rights Law* (Oxford, Oxford University Press 2011) 50-51

¹⁶⁵ *Legality of the Threat or Use of Nuclear Weapons*, Advisory Opinion [1996] I.C.J. Rep., p.226, p. 240

¹⁶⁶ N.15 (Dinstein) 228

¹⁶⁷ G. Oberleitner, *Human Rights in Armed Conflict* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press 2015) 318

¹⁶⁸ B. Klein Goldewijk, A. C. Baspineiro, P. C. Carbonari, *Dignity and Human Rights: The Implementation of Economic, Social and Cultural Rights* (Oxford, Hart Publishing 2002) 59

2.2 Distilling human rights with *ius cogens* status

Only states which accede to a treaty are bound by it, as summed up by the Latin maxim of *pacta tertiis nex nocent nex prosunt*, but even if they are not contracting parties, they are bound by rights which are considered to have customary force.¹⁶⁹ Furthermore, certain legal duties are *erga omnes* duties and all states are obligated to enforce these, irrespective of whether the conditions for establishing custom are satisfied (i.e. *opinio juris* coupled with state practice).¹⁷⁰ This has become known as the *jus cogens* doctrine which is “a norm accepted and recognized by the international community of States as a whole as a norm which no derogation is permitted...”¹⁷¹ However, it is debated which rights amount to *jus cogens*, though it is generally assumed that it includes the prohibitions of genocide, slavery, torture, ethnic cleansing, crimes against humanity, apartheid and grave violations of IHL and IHR.¹⁷² It has been argued that CA3 amounts to a *jus cogens*,¹⁷³ and some go even further and consider that IHL in its entirety amounts to *jus cogens* since IHL demonstrates “unilateral commitments to the international community.”¹⁷⁴ Yet whilst Western countries may accept that war crimes committed during NIACs amount to *jus cogens*, this view is not shared by the entire international community, for instance, China or India.¹⁷⁵ Article 124 of the Rome Statute also provides that states have seven years from ratification until Article 8 crimes

¹⁶⁹ Article 34 Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties 1969 (VCLT); cited from A. Kaczorowska-Ireland, *Public International Law* (5th ed, Abingdon, Routledge 2015) 104; also see n.29 (Kaczorowska) 118

¹⁷⁰ Also see *Barcelona Traction, Light and Power Company, Limited (Belgium v Spain)* [1970] I.C.J. Rep., p.3, p.32; T. Weatherall, *Jus cogens: International Law and Social Contract* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press 2015) xiv

¹⁷¹ Article 53 Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties 1969

¹⁷² N.170 (Weatherall) xv

¹⁷³ Remarks of Professor Waldemar Solf in the Humanitarian Law Conference: Determining Customary International Law Relative to the Conduct of Hostilities in NIACs, 2 *American University Journal of International Law & Policy* 1987, 471, 478; cited from n.34 (Crawford) 42

¹⁷⁴ See H. P. Gasser, ‘Ensuring respect for the Geneva Conventions and Protocols: The role of third states and the United Nations’ in (eds) H. Fox and M. A. Meyer, *Armed Conflict and the New Law*, Vol.II: Effecting Compliance (London, British Institute of International and Comparative Law 1993) 21; cited from B. S. Chimni, M. Masahiro, L.-A. Thio, *Asian Yearbook of International Law published under the auspices of the Foundation for the Development of International Law in ASIA (DILA), Volume 14 (2008)* (Abingdon, Routledge 2011) 96

¹⁷⁵ *Ibid* (Chimni et al) 97

apply and countries, such as France, have declared that they do not confer jurisdiction on the court in respect of Article 8 crimes, thereby calling into doubt that states comply with the *jus cogens* doctrine in the absence of treaty ratification.¹⁷⁶

2.3 IHR and state and non-state actors

When states sign human rights treaties, they assume duties and this extends to making sure that others adhere to the assumed human rights obligations.¹⁷⁷ Yet states have to transpose IHR into their domestic law, so that right holders can enforce the respective rights and they become real entitlements.¹⁷⁸

Furthermore, IHR is designed to control state behavior and IHR law only binds states and it is therefore problematic to hold non-state actors accountable.¹⁷⁹ Accordingly, as only the state is a duty bearer, whilst its subjects are the rights holder, there is a gap within IHR law, so that “the position of armed groups...remains at best unclear, and at worst non-existent.”¹⁸⁰ Hence, traditionally these rights only apply to state activities during conflicts.¹⁸¹ Whilst state conduct has become more regulated through IHR instruments, for instance, the Torture Convention, and requires states to adopt procedures to hold individuals accountable when abuse occurs and additionally international judicial platforms have been created, such as the International Criminal Court (ICC) and *ad hoc* criminal tribunals, the system to regulate non-state armed

¹⁷⁶ Ibid (Chimni et al) 97-98

¹⁷⁷ A. Føllesdal, J. K. Schaffer, G. Ulfstein, *The Legitimacy of International Human Rights Regimes: Legal, Political and Philosophical Perspectives* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press 2013) 59

¹⁷⁸ M. J. Perry, *Human Rights in the Constitutional Law of the United States* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press 2013) 20; O. De Schutter, *International Human Rights Law: Cases, Materials, Commentary* (2nd ed, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press 2014) 217

¹⁷⁹ L. Moffett, ‘Beyond Attribution: Responsibility of Armed Non-State Actors for Reparations in Northern Ireland, Colombia and Uganda’ in (eds) N. Gal-Or, C. Ryngaert, M. Noortmann, *Responsibilities of the Non-State Actor in Armed Conflict and the Market Place* (Leiden, Koninklijke Brill NV 2015) 328

¹⁸⁰ Ibid (Moffet); C. L. Sriram, O. Martin-Ortega, J. Herman, *War, Conflict and Human Rights: Theory and Practice* (2nd ed, Abingdon, Routledge 2014) 65

¹⁸¹ Ibid (Sriram et al) 66

actors is rather underdeveloped.¹⁸² This is alarming since over half of those partaking in internal conflicts are non-state parties.¹⁸³

Yet the international law concept of state responsibility has been expanded and a state can be held responsible for the acts of non-state actors when it is not diligent in preventing and investigating breaches, fails to hold perpetrators accountable and give victims remedies.¹⁸⁴

Also, when legal obligations are violated by a non-state actor which subsequently governs the state, then those responsible should be held accountable, but in practice this is improbable.¹⁸⁵

Moreover, it has incrementally been recognised that non-state actors have to adhere to IHR, even when they have not agreed this.¹⁸⁶ The UNSC has encouraged non-state actors to adhere to IHR and IHR standards, even when they are not recognised by member states, particularly when armed groups control a large area and population and have a clear political set up.¹⁸⁷ For instance, UNSC Resolution (UNSCR) 1894 (2009) requires that “parties to armed conflict comply strictly with the obligations applicable to them under international humanitarian, human rights and refugee law.”¹⁸⁸ However, to date assumption of responsibility is not mandatory, partly because of the political issue that this would confer

¹⁸² Ibid (Sriram et al) 66

¹⁸³ N.17 (Sivakumaran) 3

¹⁸⁴ Also see *Asian Agricultural Products Ltd (AAPL) v Republic of Sri Lanka* [1991] 30 I.L.M. 577; M. Ssenyonjo, M. A. Baderin, *International Human Rights Law: Six Decades after the UDHR and Beyond* (Farnham, Ashgate Publishing Ltd 2010) 410

¹⁸⁵ *Case Concerning United States Diplomatic and Consular Staff in Teheran (United States of America v Iran)* [1980] I.C.J. Rep., p.3, pp57&69-71; n.29 (Kaczorowska) 436

¹⁸⁶ A. Clapham, Human rights obligations of non-state actors in conflict situations, 88(863) *International Review of the Red Cross* 2006, 492, 492

¹⁸⁷ Report of the Special Rapporteur on extrajudicial, summary or arbitrary executions, Philip Alston; the Special Rapporteur on the right of everyone to the enjoyment of the highest attainable standard of physical and mental health, Paul Hunt; the Representative of the Secretary-General on human rights of internally displaced persons, Walter Kalin; and the Special Rapporteur on adequate housing as a component of the right to an adequate standard of living, Miloon Kathair, Mission to Lebanon and Israel (7-14 September 2006), UN Doc.a/HRC/2/7, 2 October 2006, para.19

¹⁸⁸ Also see United Nations Security Council Resolution (UNSCR); UNSCR 1019(1995), UNSCR 1034(1995); UNSCR 1400/2002; UNSCR 1464(2003); UNSCR 1468(2003); UNSCR 1564(2004); R. Arnold, N. N. R. Quénivet, *International Humanitarian Law and Human Rights Law: Towards a New Merger in International Law* (Leiden, Koninklijke NV 2008) 41

legitimacy on non-state actors.¹⁸⁹ This is particularly the case when a state labels an armed non-state group a terrorist and adopts oppressive measures against it; and additionally, it becomes difficult to include such actors within the IHR and IHL paradigm, including requiring them to voluntarily assume responsibility.¹⁹⁰ This is because armed non-state actors often perceive themselves as disadvantaged and Petrov argues that international law is best enforced through conclusion of domestic *ad hoc agreements* with armed non-state parties.¹⁹¹ However, when grave human rights breaches are committed, those responsible for non-state armed groups can be convicted at the ICC.¹⁹² Whilst individual criminal liability can be imposed, this is not the case with states, though they may have to pay reparations.¹⁹³

Military and peacekeeping personnel authorised by the UN are also duty bearers which have to adhere to IHL and IHR.¹⁹⁴ Equally, IHR should be followed by other forces which participate in the internal conflict, but which are not authorised by the UN.¹⁹⁵ Consequently, the state-centered approach of IHR significantly weakens the protective reach of IHR for civilians.¹⁹⁶

¹⁸⁹ N.186 (Clapham) 523

¹⁹⁰ D. S. Weissbrodt, C. de la Vega, *International Human Rights Law: An Introduction* (Philadelphia, University of Pennsylvania Press 2007) 239

¹⁹¹ A. O. Petrov, Non-State Actors and Law of Armed Conflict Revisited: Enforcing International Law through Domestic Engagement, 19(2) *Journal of Conflict & Security Law* 2014, 279, 316

¹⁹² M. J. Struett, 'War Crimes Trials and the Just War Tradition' in (eds) E. A. Heinze, B. J. Steele, *Ethics, Authority, and War: Non-State Actors and the Just War Tradition* (Basingstoke, Palgrave MacMillan 2009) 102

¹⁹³ *Legal Consequences of the Construction of a Wall in the Occupied Palestinian Territory*, Advisory Opinion [2004] I.C.J. Rep., p.136; C. Evans, *The Right to Reparation in International Law for Victims of Armed Conflict* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press 2012) 30

¹⁹⁴ Also see Article 20 of the UN General Assembly Resolution (UNGA) 49/59 Convention on the Safety of United Nations and Associated Personnel 1994; United Nations Human Rights Office of the High Commissioner, *International Legal Protection of Human Rights in Armed Conflict*, New York and Geneva, 2011, 1-124, 28 <http://www.ohchr.org/Documents/Publications/HR_in_armed_conflict.pdf> accessed 1st July 2015

¹⁹⁵ *Ibid* (United Nations Human Rights Office of the High Commissioner) 29

¹⁹⁶ M. K. Bulterman, W. J.M. van Genugten, *Netherlands Yearbook of International Law 2013: Crisis and International Law: Decoy or Catalyst?* (The Hague, T.M.C. Asser Press 2014) 328

2.4 IHR and IHL: a complementary, concurrent or separate relationship?

Another issue with using IHR to protect civilians is that opinion is divided about whether the relationship between IHR and IHL is complementary, concurrent or separate.¹⁹⁷ Resultantly, the connection between IHL and IHR is unclear and this makes it difficult to know and adopt the relevant law in order to afford civilians the greatest possible protection during NIACs.¹⁹⁸ Whilst the origins of both regimes have commonalities, they developed separately.¹⁹⁹ It has traditionally been assumed that IHL applies during times of war, whereas IHR applies during times of peace.²⁰⁰ Furthermore, those favouring the separationist stance consider that the objective of IHR is to avert that individuals are subjected to state abuse, whereas the objective of IHL is to minimise extreme affliction and damage.²⁰¹ Resultantly, under this view there is no concurrence or complementarity between the two regimes.

The Spanish civil war and many other internal conflicts following the WWII illustrated how civilians could suffer from NIACs and this resulted in a call for improved rules at the 1968 International Conference on Human Rights in Tehran and the UNGA starting to pass resolutions which promote observance of human rights, thereby blurring the distinction

¹⁹⁷ K. Fortin, Complementarity between the ICRC and the United Nations and international humanitarian law and international human rights law, 1948-1968, 94(888) *International Review of the Red Cross* 2012, 1433, 1433-1434; A. L. Escorihuela, Humanitarian Law and Human Rights Law: The Politics of Distinction, 19(2) *Michigan State Journal of International Law* 2011, 209, 303; H.-J. Heintze, On the relationship between human rights law protection and international humanitarian law, 86(856) *International Review of the Red Cross* 2004, 789, 813; C. Droege, The Interplay Between International Humanitarian Law and International Human Rights Law in Situations of Armed Conflict, 40 *Israel Law Review* 2007, 310, 310

¹⁹⁸ L. M. Olson, Practical Challenges of Implementing the Complementarity Between International Humanitarian and Human Rights Law - Demonstrated by the Procedural Regulation of Internment in NIAC, 40 *Case Western Reserve Journal of International Law* 2009, 437, 437; O. A. Hathaway, R. Crotofo, P. Levitz, H. Nix, W. Perdue, C. Purvis, J. Spiegel, Which Law Governs During Armed Conflict? The Relationship Between International Humanitarian Law and Human Rights Law, 96 *Minnesota Law Review* 2011-2012, 1883, 1883

¹⁹⁹ N. Prud'homme, International Humanitarian Law and International Human Rights Law: From Separation to Complementary Application, 2012 <<http://aran.library.nuigalway.ie/xmlui/handle/10379/3111>> accessed 1st July 2015

²⁰⁰ C. Stahn, Jus ad bellum, jus in bello...jus post bellum? - Rethinking the Conception of the Law of Armed Force, 17 *European Journal of International Law* 2007, 921, 922

²⁰¹ N.28 (Wilmshurst) para.3.2.1

between the wartime IHL and peacetime IHR regimes.²⁰² Yet the thorny issue is how to link the derogation threshold under IHR to the applicability of IHL since IHL permits war, whilst IHR arguably does not.²⁰³

In the Advisory Opinion on the *Legality of the Threat or Use of Nuclear Weapons*,²⁰⁴ the ICJ analysed the relationship between a specific IHR norm and an applicable IHL rule and this generated further academic interest in the relationship.²⁰⁵ Subsequently, in the *Legality of the Construction of a Wall, Advisory Opinion of 9 July 2004*,²⁰⁶ the ICJ confirmed that “as regards the relationship between [IHL] and [IHR], there are...three possible situations: some rights may be exclusively matters in international humanitarian law; others may be exclusively matters of human rights law; yet others may be matters of both these branches of international law...the Court will have to take into consideration both these branches of international law...”²⁰⁷

Yet despite this, some, including the US, contend that IHL and IHR are separate fields²⁰⁸ due to their conceptual distinction and that a merging of the two regimes creates vagueness and discord.²⁰⁹ Furthermore, states have not recognised much IHL as IHR and since states have to adopt domestic legislation to that effect, the issue is whether there is sufficient normative

²⁰² United Nations Office of Legal Affairs, Collection of Essays by Legal Advisers of States, Legal Advisers of International Organizations and Practitioners in the Field of International Law (New York, United Nations 1999) 75

²⁰³ Article 4 of the ICESCR; W. A. Schabas, *Lex Specialis-Belt and Suspenders - the Parallel Operation of Human Rights Law and the Law of Armed Conflict, and the Conundrum of Jus Ad Bellum*, 40(2) *Israel Law Review* 2007, 592, 592; N. Lubell, *Challenges in applying human rights law to armed conflict*, 87(860) *International Review of the Red Cross* 2005, 737, 752; n.188 (Arnold and Quénivet) 253

²⁰⁴ *Legality of the Threat or Use of Nuclear Weapons*, Advisory Opinion [1996] I.C.J. Rep., p.226, para.25

²⁰⁵ N.164 (Ben-Naftali) 99

²⁰⁶ *Legality of the Construction of a Wall*, Advisory Opinion [2004] I.C.J. Rep., p.136

²⁰⁷ *Ibid*, para.106

²⁰⁸ N. 197 (Heintze) 790-791; C. M. De Vois, ‘Judging Justice: Laws of War, Human Rights, and the Military Commissions Act of 2006’ in (eds) n.188 (Arnold and Quénivet) 502

²⁰⁹ *Ibid* (De Vois) 502

agreement to implement essential IHL and IHR standards and even if this is agreed in which circumstances.²¹⁰

Also, whilst Protocol I, Article 75 requires that its assurances, for instance, the prohibition against torture, are provided, as well as for important human rights,²¹¹ Protocol II has not an equivalent Article and only the preamble makes recourse to IHR treaties and conventions.²¹²

Yet Protocol II, Articles 4-6 further clarify the protective standards required pursuant to CA3.²¹³ Those, who advocate integration therefore argue that IHL includes important IHR standards within IHL, though these IHR standards can be derogated from so far as this is required by the particular circumstances.²¹⁴ Hence, under this view IHL is a particular form of human rights which spells out specific procedures i.e. is a branch of IHR, which is rooted in the fundamental concept of humanity.²¹⁵ However, the fact that states are allowed to limit human rights, as further discussed below, makes it difficult to perceive both systems as fully integrated.

An alternative approach is thus to perceive IHL and IHR as fulfilling a complementary/concurrent role, so that IHR is an exception, as opposed to a substitute for IHL.²¹⁶ This is illustrated by the decision by the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR)

²¹⁰ S. Caney, P. Jones, *Human Rights and Global Diversity* (Abingdon, Routledge 2014) 145

²¹¹ R. Kolb, G. Gaggioli, *Research Handbook on Human Rights and Humanitarian Law* (Cheltenham, Edward Elgar Publishing Ltd 2013) 259

²¹² N.17 (Sivakumaran) 83

²¹³ S. Perrakis, 'Issues of Prevention and the Development of International Humanitarian Law: From the International Criminal Tribunals for the Former Yugoslavia and Rwanda to the International Criminal Court' in (eds) M. Robinson, L.-A. Sisilianos, C. Bourlogiannē-Vraila, *The Prevention of Human Rights Violations: Contribution on the Occasion of the Twentieth Anniversary of the Marangopoulos Foundation for Human Rights (MFHR)* (The Hague, Martinus Nijhoff Publishers 2001) 77

²¹⁴ See, for example, Article 15 of the European Convention of Human Rights 1950 (ECHR); n.197 (Heintze) 790

²¹⁵ C. Tomuschat, *Human Rights between Idealims and Realism* (2nd edn, Oxford: Oxford University Press 2008) 292; n.167 (Oberleitner) 122-123

²¹⁶ N.164 (Ben-Naftali) 4

in *Loizidou v Turkey*²¹⁷ in which the ECHR was applied, as opposed to IHL, when Turkey invaded Northern Cyprus and prevented the claimant from accessing her premises.²¹⁸ IHL can also fulfill a complementary role when a particular topic is not addressed by IHR, for instance, when the Red Cross emblem can be used.²¹⁹ Nonetheless, it remains a thorny issue to determine the exact relationship between IHR and IHL.²²⁰

Yet when the test in Protocol II is not met, IHR plays an important role in safeguarding civilians. The ICJ and other courts and human rights bodies have confirmed that human rights treaties apply during armed conflicts.²²¹ In the Advisory Opinion on the *Legality of the Threat or Use of Nuclear Weapons*,²²² it was found that the ICCPR operates when there is war subject to Article 4 which permits derogations from particular Articles when there are national emergencies.²²³ The UN Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights has observed that this extends to respecting “basic economic, social and cultural rights, as part of the minimum stands of human rights...guaranteed under customary international law and...prescribed by international humanitarian law.”²²⁴ IHR protection for civilians is also incrementally enhanced due to the adoption of new conventions, such as the Convention on

²¹⁷ *Loizidou v Turkey* [1996] 21 E.H.R.R. 188

²¹⁸ N.197 (Heintze) 806

²¹⁹ D. Fleck, M. Bothe, *The Handbook of International Humanitarian Law* (3rd ed, Oxford, Oxford University Press 2013) 73

²²⁰ M. Happold, *International Humanitarian Law and Human Rights Law*, Université du Luxembourg, 24 May 2012, 1, 1 <http://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2065974> accessed 4 July 2015

²²¹ N.9 (Tonkin) 144

²²² *Legality of the Threat or Use of Nuclear Weapons*, Advisory Opinion [1996] I.C.J. Rep., p.226, para.25

²²³ *Ibid*, para. 25; also see *Legal Consequences of the Construction of a Wall in the Occupied Palestinian Territory*, Advisory Opinion [2004] I.C.J. Rep., p.136, para.106; *Armed Activities on the Territory of the Congo (Democratic Republic of the Congo v Uganda) Judgment* [2005] I.C.J. Rep., p.168, para.216

²²⁴ UN Committee on Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights, *Concluding Observations of the Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights: Israel*, E/C.12/1/Add.90, 23 May 2003; cited from F. Abrahams, M. E. Garlasco, D. Li, *Razing Rafah: Mass Home Demolitions in the Gaza Strip* (New York, Human Rights Watch 2004) 140

the Rights of the Child 1989 with the 2000 Protocol, and international human rights bodies and courts recognising the therein spelled out rights.²²⁵

2.5 Reconciling IHR and IHL conflicts and the *lex specialis* principle

The *lex specialis derogat legi generali* principle denotes that “whenever two or more norms deal with the same subject matter, priority should be given to the norm that is more specific.”²²⁶ The *lex specialis* principle is thus a tool to interpret the respective IHL and IHR rules, which sometimes conflict with each other. The principle can be interpreted in different ways.²²⁷ The general rule may provide guidance about how the specific rule should be interpreted, thereby being an elaboration of the general rule. For instance, in the Advisory Opinion about *Nuclear Weapons*,²²⁸ the ICJ expressed this view when it corroborated that “[t]he test of what is an arbitrary deprivation of life...falls to be determined by the...*lex specialis*...the law...which is designed to regulate the conduct of hostilities.”²²⁹ In the alternative, when two rules cannot be reconciled, the specific rule takes precedence, i.e. is treated as the “exception to the general rule.”²³⁰ During NIACs, IHL provides the more specific rules, though this may not always be the case, particularly when the host state maintains control.²³¹ Yet whilst the meaning of the principle, as well as its effect can be easily described in broad terms, its precise application is much more elusive.²³² Uncertainty may prevail when determining which rule constitutes the *lex specialis* or whether rules complement or collide with each other, though it has been averred that the human rights

²²⁵ *Case Concerning Armed Activities on the Territory of the Congo (Democratic Republic of the Congo v Uganda)* [2005] I.C.J. Rep., p.168, para.217; n.188 (Arnold and Quénivet) 43

²²⁶ United National General Assembly (UNGA) (International Law Commission), *Fragmentation of International Law: Difficulties Arising from the Diversification and Expansion of International Law*, UN Doc A/CN.4/L.702, 18 July 2006, para.14.2(5); cited from n.15 (Jinks et al) 36

²²⁷ *Ibid* (Jinks et al) 36

²²⁸ *Legality of Threat or Use of Nuclear Weapons Opinion*, Advisory Opinion, 8 July 1996

²²⁹ *Ibid*, para.25

²³⁰ N.219 (Fleck and Bothe) 73

²³¹ *Ibid* 75

²³² L. Pineschi, *General Principles of Law - The Role of the Judiciary* (London, Springer International Publishing 2015) 287

paradigm should be assigned more weight when the circumstances are more stable and there is greater control.²³³

Furthermore, countries, such as the US have argued that human rights have no extraterritorial effect and thus do not apply when there is a military intervention in a NIAC by another party and that the principle only applies when the threshold criteria for an armed conflict have been met.²³⁴

It has therefore been submitted that when individuals are being detained in Guantanamo Bay that the *lex specialis* is the law governing armed conflicts, despite none of the provisions in CA3 or Protocol II addressing this.²³⁵ Yet such an approach, which is modelled on IACs,²³⁶ is flawed since it cannot be justified under IHR.²³⁷ Recently the UK High Court ruled²³⁸ that Article 15 of the ECHR constitutes the *lex specialis* since IHL governing NIACs is silent on detention, thereby finding that human rights can have extraterritorial effect.²³⁹ This suggests that there has been a drive towards more convergence between IHL and IHR.²⁴⁰

2.6 Human rights limitations, derogations and reservations

²³³ N.162 (Sheeran and Rodley) 135

²³⁴ N.8 (Gill et al) 11

²³⁵ Ibid (Gill et al)

²³⁶ See Article 21 of Convention III; Article 42(1) and Article 78(1) of Convention IV

²³⁷ K. J. Heller, 'The Use and Abuse of Analogy in IHL' in (eds) J. Ohlin, *Theoretical Boundaries of Armed Conflict & Human Rights* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press 2015) 1, 1

<http://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2546359> accessed 1st September 2015

²³⁸ *Serdar Mohammed v Ministry of Defence* [2014] E.W.H.C. 1369 (QB)

²³⁹ M. Milanovic, High Court Rules that the UK Lacks IHL Detention Authority in Afghanistan, Blog of the European Journal of International Law, 3 March 2014 <<http://www.ejiltalk.org/high-court-rules-that-the-uk-lacks-ihl-detention-authority-in-afghanistan/>> accessed 2nd July 2015

²⁴⁰ A. Sari, S. Aughey, Targeting and Detention in NIAC: Serdar Mohammed and the Limits of Human Rights Convergence, 91 *International Law Studies* 2015, 60, 65

Whilst IHR do not cease to operate during NIACs, their scope and thus their effectiveness becomes limited by the possibility that states can legally limit human rights and enter derogations and reservations.²⁴¹

The idea of limiting rights and entering derogations acknowledges that there can be exceptional circumstances, which require that a balance is struck between human rights and legitimate public aims.²⁴²

Certain IHRs can be limited if this is necessary and the law provides for this and much depends on the way the right and limitation are formulated.²⁴³ Rights can thus be limited by virtue of “a definitional mechanism and/or...a rights-specific limitations clause.”²⁴⁴

The spirit of the particular human rights cannot be undermined, has to be necessary to achieve a permissible objective, such as national security or public safety, and the limitation has to be proportionate.²⁴⁵ Economic, social and cultural rights can only be limited “in so far as...compatible with the nature of these rights and solely for...promoting the general welfare in a democratic society.”²⁴⁶ The ECtHR has narrowly construed the limitation in relation to the right to life by implicitly placing reliance on IHL in order to interpret IHR.²⁴⁷ Such an approach is welcome to effectively safeguard civilians.

²⁴¹ C. M. Bailliet, K. M. Larsen, *Promoting Peace Through International Law* (Oxford, Oxford University Press 2015) 121

²⁴² N.162 (Sheeran and Rodley) 397

²⁴³ N.15 (Dinstein) 233

²⁴⁴ S. Joseph, A. McBeth, *Research Handbook on International Human Rights Law* (Cheltenham, Edward Elgar Publishing Limited 2010) 535

²⁴⁵ D. L. Shelton, *Advanced Introduction to International Human Rights Law* (Cheltenham, Edward Elgar Publishing Inc 2014) 198&200

²⁴⁶ J. M. Diller, *Securing Dignity and Freedom Through Human Rights: Article 22 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights* (Leiden, Koninklijke Brill NV 2012) 144

²⁴⁷ W. Abresch, A Human Rights Law of Internal Armed Conflict: The European Court of Human Rights in Chechnya, 16(4) *European Journal of International Law* 2005, 741, 766; E. Tamura, The Isayeva Cases of the European Court of Human Rights: The Application of International Humanitarian Law and Human Rights Law in Non-International Armed Conflicts, 10(1) *Chinese Journal of International Law* 2011, 129, 129

However, civilian protection is also undermined by derogations. Article 4(1) of the ICCPR confirms that certain duties can be derogated from when there is a public emergency and this endangers the life of the nation and the emergency is formally announced.²⁴⁸ Yet such derogation has to be “strictly required by the exigencies of the situation”, cannot be discriminatory or contravene other international law obligations and has to be notified to other ICCPR parties and states often find it difficult to meet these criteria.²⁴⁹

The derogation concept makes it possible to clearly delineate non-derogable duties, for instance, the proscription of torture.²⁵⁰ Hence, certain rights are absolute in nature and cannot be derogated from.²⁵¹ This includes economic, social and cultural rights, spelled out in the ICESCR.²⁵² However, this does not resolve the issue of interpreting the particular norm in accordance with the *lex specialis* principle.²⁵³

Moreover, the UN Human Rights Committee has opined that Article 4 of the ICCPR, which deals with derogation, should be restrictively construed and has emphasised the importance to be granted the right of *habeas corpus*.²⁵⁴ Consequently, procedural safeguards have to be provided.²⁵⁵ The death penalty can only be imposed for the worst crimes.²⁵⁶ The scope of

²⁴⁸ Also see Article 15 of the ECHR; *Lawless v Ireland* [1979-80] 1 E.H.R.R. 15, para.28

²⁴⁹ *Isayeva v Russia* [2005] 41 E.C.H.R. 38; *Ergi v Turkey* [1998] E.C.H.R. 59; A. Byrnes, M. Hayashi, C. Michaelsen, *International Law in the New Age of Globalization* (Leiden, Koninklijke Brill NV 2013) 162-163

²⁵⁰ *Ibid* (Byrnes et al) 162-163

²⁵¹ Article 4(2) of the ICCPR; Article 2(2) of the Convention against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment 1984; K. da Costa, *The Extraterritorial Application of Selected Human Rights Treaties* (Leiden Koninklijke Brill NV 2013) 257

²⁵² *Legality of the Threat or Use of Nuclear Weapons*, Advisory Opinion [1996] I.C. L. Rep., p.226, para.25; *Legal Consequences of the Construction of a Wall in the Occupied Palestinian Territory*, Advisory Opinion [2004] I.C.J. Rep., p.136; n.246 (Diller) 144

²⁵³ N.249 (Byrnes et al) 162-163

²⁵⁴ Human Rights Committee, General Comment 29: States of Emergency, UN Doc CCPR/C/21/Rev.1 Add.11 (2001); T. McDonnell, *The United States, International Law, and the Struggle Against Terrorism* (Abingdon, Routledge 2009) 108

²⁵⁵ Articles 14 and 15 of the ICCPR

²⁵⁶ Article 6(2) of the ICCPR

derogations is thus not limitless. However, a comparison of the non-derogable rights in Article 4 of the ICCPR and those spelled out in the ECHR²⁵⁷ shows that the transposition of these rights is more limited at the regional level.²⁵⁸ The problem is that derogation from those rights which are not absolute rights can undermine protection for civilians, particularly since it is up to states to determine the extent of the derogation.²⁵⁹

Furthermore, states cannot rely on derogations to prevent the imposition of individual criminal responsibility or state responsibility.²⁶⁰ State responsibility may be nonetheless averted for contractors which fulfill coercive functions due to various factors, such as “the limited reach of positive IHL obligations...and the complex questions extraterritorial application poses.”²⁶¹

The effectiveness of IHR is further undermined by reservations, which states may choose to enter in respect of particular Articles.²⁶² However, the treaty cannot proscribe the reservation and it cannot frustrate the treaty’s aim and purpose,²⁶³ though contracting states may nevertheless enter what may be perceived as invalid reservations since such an approach promotes ratification of human rights treaties.²⁶⁴ This can result in the treaty applying without

²⁵⁷ See Articles 2(2) and 15 of the ECHR

²⁵⁸ Geneva Academy, Derogation from human rights treaties in situations of emergency, 2015 <http://www.geneva-academy.ch/RULAC/derogation_from_human_rights_treaties_in_situations_of_emergency.php> accessed 5th July 2015

²⁵⁹ A. Bullard, *Human Rights in Crisis* (Aldershot, Ashgate Publishing Limited 2008) 61

²⁶⁰ United Nations Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, International Bar Association, *Human Rights In The Administration Of Justice: A Manual On Human Rights For Judges, Prosecutors and Lawyers* (New York, United Nations Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights 2003) 17

²⁶¹ C. Hoppe, Passing the Buck: State Responsibility for Private Military Companies, 19(5) *European Journal of International Law* 2008, 989, 1014

²⁶² R. Goodman, Human Rights Treaties, Invalid Reservations, and State Consent, 96 *American Journal of International Law* 2002, 530, 559

²⁶³ Article 19 of the Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties 1969; O. Corten, P. Klein, *The Vienna Conventions on the Law of Treaties: A Commentary, Volume 1* (Oxford, Oxford University Press 2011) 483

²⁶⁴ N.262 (Goodman) 559

the reservation through the process of severance, but also in the entire treaty becoming no longer binding, thereby leaving civilians unprotected.²⁶⁵ However, the UN Human Rights Committee consider the “object and purpose rule” sufficient to prevent reservations.²⁶⁶ Similarly, to the “object and purpose rule”, when an IHR is considered a *jus cogens*, no reservation can be entered.²⁶⁷ Yet the assertion that there is a peremptory norm is difficult since “[t]he international community 'as whole' "directly or indirectly varies with the arbitrary wills of the state members.”²⁶⁸

2.7 Summary

Despite IHR extending to NIACs, civilians are insufficiently protected by IHR: There are different IHR sources; a grey penumbra surrounds the *jus cogens* doctrine, which make it difficult to know with absolute certainty which rights are covered; non-state actors are insufficiently included by the IHR regime; the relationship between IHR and IHL is unclear and disputed, the *lex specialis* principle favours IHL at the expense of IHR; and human rights can be limited, derogated from and totally disregarded by a state which has entered reservations.

²⁶⁵ P. Alston, R. Goodman, *International Human Rights* (Oxford, Oxford University Press 2013) 1113

²⁶⁶ F. F. Martin, S. J. Schnably, R. Wilson, J. Simon, M. Tushnet, *International Human Rights and Humanitarian Law: Treaties, Cases, and Analysis* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press 2006) 227

²⁶⁷ U. Linderfalk, The Effect of *Jus cogens* Norms: Whoever Opened Pandora's Box, Did You Ever Think About the Consequences? 18(5) *European Journal of International Law* 2008, 853, 868

²⁶⁸ W. E. Conklin, The Peremptory Norms of the International Community, 23(3) *European Journal of International Law* 2012, 837, 837 & 860

Chapter 3: The duty of states to safeguard civilians during NIACs and oversight by the international community

3.0 Introduction

Civilians can only be safeguarded during NIACs if states are required to enforce the respective rights, which the IHL and IHR regimes spell out and the international community reinforces this. This chapter therefore investigates which procedures have been created and whether these are sufficient.

3.1 The domestic mechanisms to safeguard civilians and problems with these mechanisms

Domestic mechanisms are necessary to enforce the rights, which the IHL and IHR regimes afford to civilians during NIACs. Duties have to be therefore imposed on all those, who violate IHL and IHR. Breaches of these duties have to be investigated, prosecuted and punished and victims, including their families, should be entitled to seek remedies.

Whilst it is pertinent that an investigation is conducted in accordance with the universal principles of impartiality, effectiveness, promptness and independence, there is exiguous written law available which provides guidance, even though investigation and prosecution are

mandated by virtue of customary and treaty law.²⁶⁹ As a corollary, the duty to investigate is by no means clear. For instance, it is debatable what triggers an investigation, in which circumstances fact-finding activities or criminal investigations should be commenced, to what extent the above-discussed IHR principles, such as military necessity, impact the obligation to conduct an investigation or the extent to which IHR apply.²⁷⁰ Furthermore, when the state commits IHR and/or IHL breaches, it is unrealistic to assume that the duty to investigate is fully discharged since “no system can investigate itself.”²⁷¹

Whilst states have to charge and punish those, who commit “grave breaches” during IACs, CA3 does not spell out such a duty and whilst Article 6 of Protocol II discusses penal prosecutions and mandates a fair hearing, its fifth paragraph states that authorities should “grant the broadest possible amnesty...”²⁷² However, this lacuna in the law governing NIACs has been partly closed by the Rome Statute, which lists certain serious types of war crimes.²⁷³ Consequently, for certain war crimes, such as genocide, perpetrators have to be punished and other states have also exercised universal jurisdiction and have tried perpetrators in their local courts.²⁷⁴ It has therefore been argued that this has become a customary rule of international law.²⁷⁵

²⁶⁹ M. N. Schmitt, Investigating Violations of International law in Armed Conflict, 2 *Harvard National Security Journal* 2011, 31, 82

²⁷⁰ A. Cohen, Y. Shany, ‘Beyond the Grave Breaches Regime: The Duty to Investigate Alleged Violations of International Law Governing Armed Conflicts’ in (eds) M. N. Schmitt, L. Arimatsu, *Yearbook of International Humanitarian Law 2011 - Volume 14* (The Hague, Springer 2012) 37-84, 39-40

²⁷¹ Israel's Report to the UN Misstates the Truth, B'Tselem, 4 February 2010
<http://www.btselem.org/gaza_strip/20100204_israels_report_to_un> accessed 25th July 2015; cited from n.269 (Schmitt) 32

²⁷² Cited from J. Wouters, The Obligation to Prosecute International Law Crimes, Institute for International Law, undated, 1, 5-6 <<https://www.law.kuleuven.be/iir/nl/onderzoek/opinies/obligationtoprosecute.pdf>> accessed 25th July 2015

²⁷³ *Ibid*, 6

²⁷⁴ International Committee of the Red Cross, *Customary International Humanitarian Law* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press 2005) 603

²⁷⁵ *Ibid*

Nonetheless, when IHL and IHR violations are committed which are not perceived as serious, the duty to investigate and prosecute may not be triggered, thereby leaving civilians unprotected.²⁷⁶

The UNGA has affirmed that the state owes victims²⁷⁷ a duty to avert breaches, to investigate them, to enable victims to seek effective and equal justice and to be awarded effective remedies, including reparation.²⁷⁸ Nonetheless, the duty to compensate victims for a breach of CA3, the rules in Protocol II and particular customary international rules is controversial.²⁷⁹

Whilst reliance may be placed on the *Factory at Chorzów* case,²⁸⁰ in which it was observed that “the breach of an engagement involves an obligation to make reparation in an adequate form”,²⁸¹ nationals will find it difficult to evoke this international law principle against their own state in the absence of an effective domestic or international mechanism.²⁸² This is despite the right to a remedy being recognised in Article 2(3) of the ICCPR and in other treaties,²⁸³ as well as by the UNGA.²⁸⁴ The ICC has affirmed that reparation can be sought and its Statute enables the court to award remedies, albeit only within the narrow confines of

²⁷⁶ W. A. Schabas, Punishment of Non-State Actors in NIAC, 26(3) *Fordham International Law Journal* 2002, 907, 911

²⁷⁷ Also see para.8 of the United Nations General Assembly Resolution 60/147 of 16 December 2005, Basic Principles and Guidelines on the Right to a Remedy and Reparation for Victims of Gross Violations of International Human Rights Law and Serious Violations of International Humanitarian Law

²⁷⁸ See para.3 of the United Nations General Assembly Resolution 60/147 of 16 December 2005, Basic Principles and Guidelines on the Right to a Remedy and Reparation for Victims of Gross Violations of International Human Rights Law and Serious Violations of International Humanitarian Law

²⁷⁹ C. McCarthy, *Reparations and Victim Support in the International Criminal Court* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press 2012) 25

²⁸⁰ *Chorzów Factory Case (Jurisdiction) (Germany v. Poland)* (1927) P.C.I.J., Ser. A, No. 9

²⁸¹ *Ibid*, at p.21

²⁸² N.279 (McCarthy) 25-26

²⁸³ Article 14 of the Convention against Torture and other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment 1984

²⁸⁴ United Nations General Assembly Resolution 40/34 (1985), Declaration of Basic Principles of Justice for Victims of Crime and Abuse of Power; United Nations General Assembly Resolution 60/147 of 16 December 2005, Basic Principles and Guidelines on the Right to a Remedy and Reparation for Victims of Gross Violations of International Human Rights Law and Serious Violations of International Humanitarian Law

its jurisdiction.²⁸⁵ Furthermore, Article 13 of the ECHR, Articles 10 and 25 of the American Convention on Human Rights (ACHR) and Article 7(1)(a) of the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (ACHPR) require that states provide individuals with a remedy.²⁸⁶ However, the “Arab League’s Human Rights Court will not bring justice to victims of violations” since only states can make complaints, which in reality hardly happens, especially in the case of NIACs.²⁸⁷ Even when individuals can rely on regional human rights, it is unclear whether armed groups during NIACs are required to make reparations, unlike in IACs, where this is expressly provided.²⁸⁸

Furthermore, the award of individual compensation can be fraught with difficulties and, for instance, the Internal Rules of the Extraordinary Chambers in the Courts of Cambodia only permit collective awards, but this may not be an effective remedy for marginalised individuals with specific needs.²⁸⁹ Nonetheless, this may be a pragmatic solution to overcome the issue that a war-torn country or opposition group has not got the financial means to compensate the victim and their families. Resultantly, for the majority of IHL and IHR violations, civilians will be unable to obtain a remedy, particularly when states have further curtailed human rights by virtue of a derogation clause.²⁹⁰

²⁸⁵ *Legal Consequences of the Construction of a Wall in the Occupied Palestinian Territory*, Advisory Opinion [2004] I.C.J. Rep., p.136, paras152–153

²⁸⁶ N.32 (Henckaerts and Doswald-Beck) 546

²⁸⁷ International Commission of Jurists, Arab League’s Human Rights Court will not bring justice to victims of violations, 9 September 2014 <<http://www.icj.org/arab-leagues-human-rights-court-will-not-bring-justice-to-victims-of-violations/>> accessed 23rd July 2015

²⁸⁸ See Article 91 of Protocol I; n.179 (Gal-Or et al) 327

²⁸⁹ L. Moffett, *Justice for Victims Before the International Criminal Court* (Abingdon, Routledge 2014) 179

²⁹⁰ See Article 15 of the ECHR; n.3 (Perna) 84

3.2 Civilian protection through international oversight mechanisms and problems with these mechanisms

International oversight mechanisms are important to safeguard civilians during NIACs.

3.2.1 The UN

Already in 1946, the UNSC confirmed that its jurisdiction could extend to internal matters when international security and peace were at risk.²⁹¹ For instance, the UNSC classified the NIACs in Iraq,²⁹² Rwanda,²⁹³ Kosovo²⁹⁴ and in Bosnia-Herzegovina,²⁹⁵ as constituting a threat to international security and peace, so that Chapter VII of the UN Charter could be evoked and military force could be used by individual member states, a coalition of states or through regional arrangements pursuant to Article 42 of the UN Charter.²⁹⁶

Military action has been taken, even when the UNSC has not explicitly authorised this, on the basis that this is necessary to prevent a humanitarian catastrophe.²⁹⁷ However, this “responsibility to protect” approach, as illustrated by the intervention in Iraq, has been

²⁹¹ United Nations Security Council Resolution 4 (1946); K. Manusama, *The United Nations Security Council in the Post-Cold War Era: Applying the Principle of Legality* (Leiden, Koninklijke Brill NV 2006) 56

²⁹² United Nations Security Council Resolution 688 (1991), para.1

²⁹³ United Nations Security Council Resolution 918 (1994), preamble, para.8

²⁹⁴ United Nations Security Council Resolution 1199 (1998), preamble, para.7

²⁹⁵ United Nations Security Council Resolution 770 (1992), preamble, para.5

²⁹⁶ N.22 (Fischer et al) 160-161; L. Gelot, *Legitimacy, Peace Operations and Global-regional Security: The African Union-United Nations Partnership in Darfur* (Abingdon, Routledge 2012) 30

²⁹⁷ A. Hehir, *The Responsibility to Protect: Rhetoric, Reality and the Future of Humanitarian Intervention* (Basingstoke, Palgrave MacMillan 2012) 44

criticised for resulting in “overzealous military intervention for insufficient humanitarian reasons.”²⁹⁸ In addition, it may be viewed as a tool for regime change and, e.g., in Libya NATO's humanitarian intervention had this effect, just like the French-led military action in Cote d'Ivoire.²⁹⁹ This runs counter to the concepts of non-interference³⁰⁰ and sovereign equality³⁰¹ and may be perceived as “the rule of hegemonism...”³⁰² Opinion is thus divided, suggesting that no such customary rule has yet emerged.³⁰³

Adoption of UNSCRs may favour a particular side, for instance, in Angola the resolution was directed against the non-state troops.³⁰⁴ Equally, the UNSC may adopt a resolution to authorise “all necessary measures” to safeguard civilians.³⁰⁵ The issue is that the UNSC does not authorise intervention on humanitarian grounds or peacekeeping troops whenever this may appear warranted.³⁰⁶ Resultantly, the UNSC has been criticised for not acting as a “human rights protector”, thereby opening the door to other states or coalitions of states intervening in a biased and selective manner when this serves their interests.³⁰⁷ Amnesty International reports that human rights violations were committed by the US-led coalition which intervened in Iraq, partly on humanitarian grounds, and without full accountability

²⁹⁸ Ibid (Hehir) 44; T. G. Weiss, *Humanitarian Intervention* (2nd ed, Cambridge, Polity Press 2012) 56

²⁹⁹ A. Hehir, R. Murray, *Libya, the Responsibility to Protect and the Future of Humanitarian Intervention* (Basingstoke, Palgrave MacMillan 2013) 215

³⁰⁰ Article 2(7) of the UN Charter

³⁰¹ Article 2(1) of the UN Charter

³⁰² United General Assembly A/54/PV.8 (1999) 16; cited from L. Glanville, ‘Armed humanitarian intervention and the problem of abuse after Libya’ in (eds) D. E. Scheid, *The Ethics of Armed Humanitarian Intervention* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press 2014) 151

³⁰³ J. Baylis, S. Smith, P. Owens, *The Globalization of World Politics: An Introduction to International Relations* (Oxford, Oxford University Press 2011) 513

³⁰⁴ United Nations Security Council Resolution 1127 (1997); also see United Nations Security Council Resolution 2098 (2013); United Nations Security Council Resolution 2100 (2013)

³⁰⁵ United Nations Security Council Resolution 2127 (2013); cited from n.15 (Dinstein) 92

³⁰⁶ F. A. Agwu, The Challenge of Humanitarian Intervention since Rwanda, Council of Councils, 6 August 2014 <http://www.cfr.org/councilofcouncils/global_memos/p33324> accessed 23rd July 2015

³⁰⁷ D. Wallace, D. Silander, *International Organizations and the Implementation of the Responsibility to Protect, The humanitarian crisis in Syria* (Abingdon, Routledge 2015) 20; A. Hehir, *Humanitarian Intervention: An Introduction* (2nd ed, Basingstoke, Palgrave MacMillan 2013) 252

being established for these abuses.³⁰⁸ For instance, coalition forces used “American depleted uranium weapons.”³⁰⁹

Moreover, the UNSC has authorised peacekeeping operations, despite such a power not being spelled out in the UN Charter.³¹⁰

International accountability has been promoted by the UNSC through the creation of international tribunals,³¹¹ and hybrid courts³¹² and special courts,³¹³ so that the most serious offences could be tried.³¹⁴ The authority to create the ICTR and ICTY has been based on Article 41 of the UN Charter i.e. to act as a tool to reinstate and preserve peace.³¹⁵ Yet just like with peacekeeping missions, these tribunals and courts have not been created for all NIACs.

³⁰⁸ Amnesty International, Iraq: A decade of abuses, Report, 11 March 2013

<<http://www.amnestyusa.org/research/reports/iraq-a-decade-of-abuses>> accessed 21st July 2015

³⁰⁹ J. LaForge, Iraq’s Depleted Uranium Threat: USA’s Deadly Legacy, Global Research, 25 June 2015

<<http://www.globalresearch.ca/iraqs-depleted-uranium-threat-usas-deadly-legacy/5388703>> accessed 25th July 2015

³¹⁰ H. Nasu, K. Rubenstein, *Legal Perspectives on Security Institutions* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press 2015) 169

³¹¹ United Nations Security Council Resolution 808 (1993) on the International Criminal Tribunal for the Former Yugoslavia; United Nations Security Council Resolution 995 (1994), International Criminal Tribunal for Rwanda

³¹² United Nations Security Council Resolution 1664 (2006); United Nations Security Council Resolution 1757 (2007); United Nations Security Council Resolution 1315 (2000)

³¹³ United Nations Security Council Resolution 1315 (2000); United Nations General Assembly Resolution 57/228(B) (2003)

³¹⁴ United Nations Security Council Resolution 808 (1993) on the International Criminal Tribunal for the Former Yugoslavia; United Nations Security Council Resolution 995 (1994), International Criminal Tribunal for Rwanda; C. Ku, H. K. Jacobson, *Democratic Accountability and the Use of Force in International Law* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press 2002) 374

³¹⁵ *The Prosecutor v Dusko Tadic a/k/a 'Dule'*, Case No. IT-94-1, Appeals Chamber, Decision on the Defense Motion for Interlocutory Appeal on Jurisdiction, 2 October 1995; *Prosecutor v Joseph Kanyabashi*, Case No. ICTR 96-15-T, Decision on the Defence Motion on Jurisdiction, 18 June 1997; B. Fassbender, *Securing Human Rights?: Achievements and Challenges of the UN Security Council* (Oxford, Oxford University Press 2011) 59; C. Focarelli, *International Law as Social Construct: The Struggle for Global Justice* (Oxford, Oxford University Press 2012) 486

The UNGA also plays an important role to protect civilians. The UNGA discusses armed conflicts which destabilise international peace and security with members and the UNSC and makes recommendations and brings matters to the attention of the UNSC.³¹⁶ A UNGA resolution may expressly observe that there is an armed conflict.³¹⁷ A state may be urged to take all measures to stop human rights violations.³¹⁸ The UNGA passes resolutions to call on states and other parties to adhere to applicable conventions in order to avert human suffering.³¹⁹ Recent UNGA resolutions have treated armed groups as having IHR duties.³²⁰ Moreover, the UNGA has affirmed the importance of punishing war criminals and perpetrators of crimes against humanity, as well as particular human rights.³²¹ For instance, to know “the fate of loved ones lost in armed conflicts.”³²² In the case of Libya, the UNGA suspended Libya from being a member of the Human Rights Council.³²³ In many of the resolutions, the UNGA has drawn no distinction between the types of conflict, but has simply required that IHR and IHL are being respected, thereby promoting a broader scope of protection than afforded by CA3 and Protocol II.³²⁴ However, UNGA resolutions are non-binding since it is a political body and is better understood as a “voice of world opinion.”³²⁵ This erodes the usefulness of UNGA resolutions as a mechanism to safeguard civilians.³²⁶

³¹⁶ Articles 10-11 of the UN Charter

³¹⁷ UNGA Res 37/185 (1982), UNGA Resolution 40/140 (1985); n.17 (Sivakumaran) 198

³¹⁸ For instance, see UNGA Resolution 40/140 (1985)

³¹⁹ See, for example, UNGA Resolution 2675 (1970); D. Schindler, J. Toman, *The Laws of Armed Conflicts* (Lancaster, Kluwer Academic Publishers 1988) 267

³²⁰ D. Fleck, ‘Humanitarian Protection Against Non-State Actors’ in (eds) J. A. Fowein, K. Scharioth, I. Winkelmann, R. Wolfram, *Verhandeln für den Frieden - Negotiating for Peace: Liber Amicorum Tono Eitel* (Springer, 2003) 69; n.17 (Sivakumaran) 477

³²¹ United Nations General Assembly Resolution 2583 (XXIV) (1969), Question of the punishment of war criminals and of persons who have committed crimes against humanity

³²² UNGA Resolution 3220 (1974), preambular para.8; cited from M. Jacques, *Armed Conflict and Displacement: The Protection of Refugees and Displaced Persons under International Humanitarian Law* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press 2012) 204

³²³ UNGA Resolution 65/265 (2011); n.23 (Watkin and Norris) 376

³²⁴ N.34 (Crawford) 40-41

³²⁵ G. J. Kerwin, The Role of United Nations General Assembly Resolutions in Determining Principles of International Law in United States Courts, *Duke Law Journal* 1983, 876, 899

³²⁶ M. D. Öberg, The Legal Effect of Resolutions of the UN Security Council and General Assembly in the Jurisprudence of the ICJ, 16(5) *The European Journal of International Law* 2006, 879, 884

Additionally, international oversight is being promoted by the office of the UN Secretary General. The Secretary General can be requested by the UNSC or UNGA to conduct investigations.³²⁷ He can notify the UNSC when the maintenance of peace and security are being threatened.³²⁸ This implies the power to collect information and undertake inquiries.³²⁹ He may be perceived as the “English bobby” i.e. a police officer who lacks the armoury and can therefore not issue binding decisions about which parties are responsible or impose sanctions unilaterally.³³⁰

Furthermore, international oversight has been created through the UN Human Rights Council, which was previously the Commission on Human Rights.³³¹ Its role is to facilitate that IHR are universally protected, including by identifying serious human rights abuses and issuing recommendations, encouraging education, providing technical assistance and advisory services, and making suggestions to the UNGA.³³² For instance, the then Commission reported about the situation of human rights in Chechnya.³³³ Yet its members have been critiqued for casting votes in blocs, as opposed to addressing particular matters, so that human rights violations are not being highlighted for fear of undermining security and economic interests.³³⁴ Even countries which do not fully adhere to human rights standards are

³²⁷ Articles 34 & 99 of the UN Charter; United Nations, *Pacific Settlements of Disputes* (Chapter VI), *Repertoire of the Practice of the Security Council*, 2015 <<http://www.un.org/en/sc/repertoire/settlements.shtml>> accessed 1st August 2015

³²⁸ Article 99 of the UN Charter; *ibid* (United Nations)

³²⁹ A. W. Cordier, W. Foote, *Public Papers of the Secretaries General of the United Nations, Volume I: Trygve Lie 1946-1953* (Columbia, Columbia University Press 1969) 46; L. Gordenker, *The UN Secretary-General and Secretariat* (2nd ed, Abingdon, Routledge 2010) 39

³³⁰ *Ibid* (Gordenker) 39

³³¹ B. G. Ramcharan, *The UN Human Rights Council* (Abingdon, Routledge 2011) 17

³³² *Ibid* (Ramcharan) 30

³³³ United Nations Commission on Human Rights, *The situation of human rights in the Republic of Chechnya of the Russian Federation*, Report of the Secretary-General, Fifth-second session, E.CN.4/1996/13, 26 March 1996 <http://www1.umn.edu/humanrts/commission/country52/1996_13.htm> accessed 24th July 2015

³³⁴ L. Vriens, *Troubles Plague UN Human Rights Council*, Council on Foreign Relations, 13 May 2009 <<http://www.cfr.org/international-organizations-and-alliances/troubles-plague-un-human-rights-council/p9991#p2>> accessed 25th July 2015

granted membership.³³⁵ Nonetheless, a significant amount of its resolutions make recourse to IHL.³³⁶ Moreover, the Council has responded more swiftly than the Commission to emergencies, for instance, by holding special sessions and creating fact-finding missions or commissions of inquiry.³³⁷ Yet the commission of inquiry dealing with Libya was understaffed and had already used up all of its funds when the conflict became more intense.³³⁸ Furthermore, the Council cannot directly intervene in armed conflicts to avert humanitarian catastrophes.

The UN High Commissioner for Human Rights fulfils another important oversight function as the “leading voice of the U.N. system on human rights issues”.³³⁹ The Commissioner and its office are entrusted with human rights matters, ranging from safeguarding human rights, issuing reports, making recommendations to averting human rights abuses.³⁴⁰ Yet not many resources are being committed by member states, so that important functions, such as having a good field presence, cannot be fully developed.³⁴¹

3.2.2 The ICJ

³³⁵ Global Policy Forum, Human Rights Council, 2015 <<https://www.globalpolicy.org/un-reform/un-reform-topics/human-rights-council.html>> accessed 25th July 2015

³³⁶ P. Maurer, ICRC and Human Rights Council: complementary activities, respect for differences, International Committee of the Red Cross, 26 February 2013

<<https://www.icrc.org/eng/resources/documents/statement/2013/ihl-human-rights-council.htm>> accessed 25th July 2015

³³⁷ See, for instance, Human Rights Council Decision S-4/101 (13 December 2006); n.129 (Oberleitner) 253

³³⁸ S. Nossel, How High Is the New High Commissioner? Foreign Policy, 9 June 2014

<<http://foreignpolicy.com/2014/06/09/how-high-is-the-new-high-commissioner/>> accessed 24th July 2015

³³⁹ Human Rights Watch, Response to Criticism of the U.N. High Commissioner for Human Rights, Letter from Human Rights Watch to Secretary Rice, 14 December 2005 <<https://www.hrw.org/news/2005/12/14/response-criticism-un-high-commissioner-human-rights>> accessed 25th July 2015

³⁴⁰ D. P. Forsythe, *Encyclopedia of Human Rights: Volume 1* (Oxford, Oxford University Press 2009) 175

³⁴¹ F. D. Gaer, C. L. Broecker, *The United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights: Conscience for the World* (Leiden, Koninklijke Brill NV 2014) 39

States, which are parties to the Geneva Conventions, as well as Protocol II, have to fulfil their treaty obligations in good faith.³⁴² When these are breached, they commit a wrongful act for which the state can be held responsible.³⁴³ The problem is that accountability can only be achieved for internationally wrongful acts committed by states and whilst Article 8 of the Draft Articles on State Responsibility extends the concept of state to situations where non-state actors are “acting on the instructions or, or under the direction or control of, that state”, this does not ensure that opposition groups can be held responsible.³⁴⁴ When the ICJ finds that an internationally wrongful act has been committed, reparation has to be made, though in the context of NIACs, this may be challenging to determine.³⁴⁵

Moreover, Article 34(1) of the Statute of the ICJ provides that the Court is “open to the states parties”, so that victims of IHL and IHR abuse have no *locus standi*. Hence, claims can only be brought by injured states,³⁴⁶ but it is unlikely that other states have been harmed as a result of a NIAC.³⁴⁷ Yet the ICJ has not just contentious jurisdiction, but also advisory jurisdiction, though these opinions are non-binding.³⁴⁸

3.2.3 The ICC

International accountability for breaches of IHL and IHR during NIACs are particularly achieved through the ICC, which has jurisdiction in respect of particular crimes.³⁴⁹ In contrast

³⁴² M. Fitzmaurice, D. Sarooshi, *Issues of State Responsibility Before International Judicial Institutions* (Portland, Hart Publishing 2004) 85

³⁴³ Article 1 of the International Law Commission, Draft Articles on the Responsibility of International Organisations, UN Doc. 1/59/10, 99; J. Crawford, *The International Law Commission's Articles on State Responsibility, Introduction, Text and Commentaries* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press 2002) 77

³⁴⁴ T. Reinold, *Sovereignty and the Responsibility to Protect: The Power of Norms and the norms of the powerful* (Abingdon, Routledge 2013) 93

³⁴⁵ G. Dahloff, *International Court of Justice, Digest of Judgments and Advisory Opinions, Canon and Case Law 1946-2012* (Leiden, Koninklijke Brill NV 2012) 1800

³⁴⁶ *South West Africa Cases (Ethiopia and Liberia v South Africa)* [1966] I.C.J. Rep., p.6

³⁴⁷ T. Hillier, *Sourcebook on Public International Law* (London, Cavendish Publishing Ltd 1998) 356

³⁴⁸ L. A. Malone, *International Law* (New York, Aspen Publishers 2008) 25

³⁴⁹ N.12 (Cullen) 161

to the ICJ, the ICC has not got jurisdiction in respect of states, but only over individuals,³⁵⁰ and can hold a person criminally responsible and punish the person for this.³⁵¹ This includes “the remote principal or the non-physical perpetrator” i.e. joint and indirect perpetrators, so that those who have masterminded mass abuse can be brought to justice.³⁵²

Yet the ICC has only jurisdiction in respect genocide, crimes against humanity, war crimes and the crime of aggression i.e. the most serious crimes.³⁵³ However, the crime of aggression is not yet being prosecuted due to Article 5(2) of the Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court 1998 requiring a definition of the term and whilst this was agreed in Kampala in 2010, the ICC’s jurisdiction will only commence on 1 January 2017.³⁵⁴

For the ICC to have jurisdiction, the crime must be committed by a national of a state party or in its territory,³⁵⁵ except when a referral is made by the UNSC.³⁵⁶ Only state parties or the UNSC can refer cases to an independent prosecutor, though the independent prosecutor has been given a *proprio motu* power i.e. can commence investigations; however the pre-trial chamber can revoke such a decision and the UNSC can defer or stay investigations for one year, irrespective of whether a state has referred a case or the independent prosecutor has

³⁵⁰ Articles 1 & 25(1) of the Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court 1998; M. C. Bassiouni, *Introduction to International Criminal Law: Second Revised Edition* (Leiden, Koninklijke Brill NV 2013) 660; C. Damgaard, *Individual Criminal Responsibility for Core International Crimes: Selected Pertinent Issues* (Berlin, Springer-Verlag 2008) 121

³⁵¹ Article 25(3) of the Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court 1998

³⁵² See Article 25(3)(a) of the Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court 1998; cited from E. Van Sliedregt, ‘Perpetration and Participation in Article 25(3) of the Statute of the International Criminal Court’ in (eds) C. Stahn, *The Law and Practice of the International Criminal Court* (Oxford, Oxford University Press 2015) 1-2 <http://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2492710> accessed 25th July 2015

³⁵³ Article 5 of the Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court 1998

³⁵⁴ D. Akande, What Exactly was Agreed in Kampala on the Crime of Aggression? Blog of the European Journal of International Law, 21 June 2010 <<http://www.ejiltalk.org/what-exactly-was-agreed-in-kampala-on-the-crime-of-aggression/>> accessed 25th July 2015; M. Politi, The ICC and the Crime of Aggression, A Dream that Came Through and the Reality Ahead, 10(1) *Journal of International Criminal Justice* 2012, 267, 267

³⁵⁵ Article 12(2) of the Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court 1998; n.350 (Bassiouni) 658

³⁵⁶ Article 13(b) of the Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court 1998; J. Doria, H.-P. Gasser, M. C. Bassiouni, *The Legal Regime of the International Criminal Court: Essays in Honour of Professor Igor Blishchenko* (Leiden, Koninklijke Brill NV 2009) 474

started it.³⁵⁷ Yet justice for victims can be undermined by the ICC's prosecutor having discretion to decide which conflicts and persons should be investigated, also leading to accusations of “bullying Africa”³⁵⁸ and “juridical politics” and “political justice.”³⁵⁹ In addition, self-referrals have been made, despite this not being envisaged.³⁶⁰ The issue with self-referrals is that these may be motivated by political interests i.e. to harm political opponents.³⁶¹ This may lead to allegations that the ICC is not independent and investigates one side more than the other or that the state has entered into a secret deal with the court.³⁶² Another problem is that other states may be declined to refer cases about IHR and IHL violations which have not been committed in their territory.

The ICC can award reparations in the form of compensation, restitution and rehabilitation against a perpetrator³⁶³ or by virtue of the Victims Trust Fund.³⁶⁴ The underlying approach is not based on retributive, but “restorative justice” and is more “community-oriented” and directed at achieving reconciliation, rather than punishment.³⁶⁵ Mass claims and the trust fund

³⁵⁷ Article 15 of the Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court 1998; K. Quadri, The Proprio motu power of the ICC Prosecutor: the reason some states have refused to ratify the Rome Statute, 2(1) *International Journal of Humanities and Management Sciences* 2014, 11, 11&14

³⁵⁸ J. Wouters, K. Chan, Policies, Not Politics: The Pursuit of Justice in Prosecutorial Strategy at the International Criminal Court, Leuven Centre for Global Governance Studies, Working Paper No.95, July 2012, 1, 1

³⁵⁹ T. Murithi, ‘Between Political Justice and Judicial Politics: Charting a Way Forward for the African Union and the International Criminal Court’ in (eds) G. Werle, L. Fernandez, M. Vormbaum, *Africa and the International Criminal Court* (London, Springer 2014) 179, 180

³⁶⁰ Article 14 of the Rome Statute; P. Akhavan, The Lord's Resistance Army Case: Uganda's Submission of the First State Referral to the International Criminal Court, 99(2) *American Journal of International Law* 2005, 403, 403; P. Wegner, Self-Referrals and Lack of Transparency at the ICC – The Case of Northern Uganda, *Justice in Conflict*, 4 October 2011 <<http://justiceinconflict.org/2011/10/04/self-referrals-and-lack-of-transparency-at-the-icc-%E2%80%93-the-case-of-northern-uganda/>> accessed 26th July 2015

³⁶¹ P. Wegner, Self-Referrals and Lack of Transparency at the ICC – The Case of Northern Uganda, *Justice in Conflict*, 4 October 2011 <<http://justiceinconflict.org/2011/10/04/self-referrals-and-lack-of-transparency-at-the-icc-%E2%80%93-the-case-of-northern-uganda/>> accessed 2nd September 2015

³⁶² Ibid (Wegner)

³⁶³ Article 75(2) of the Rome Statute

³⁶⁴ Article 79 of the Rome Statute; L. M. Keller, Seeking Justice at the International Criminal Court: Victims' Reparations, 29 *Thomas Jefferson Law Review* 2007, 189, 190; A. Fenyves, E. Karner, H. Koziol, E. Steiner, *Tort Law in the Jurisprudence of the European Court of Human Rights* (Berlin, Walter de Gruyter GmbH & Ko KG 2011) 383-384

³⁶⁵ Ibid (Keller) 190

lacking sufficient resources means that awards are small and symbolic, so that harm is not fully remedied.³⁶⁶

3.2.4 IHR treaty bodies

The implementation of the main IHR treaties is being overseen by ten UN human rights treaty bodies.³⁶⁷ States are required to submit reports to the bodies which make recommendations.³⁶⁸ The bodies publish general comments in order to provide additional guidance.³⁶⁹ Special procedures' mandates are given to Special Rapporteurs to investigate and report about human rights matters in particular countries or about specific human rights topics.³⁷⁰ The ICJ has referred to these reports and national courts can place reliance on these.³⁷¹ However, the assessment of these reports is often delayed because states submit them late and because these reports have to be translated into three main languages, which in 2010 cost \$17.5 million.³⁷²

³⁶⁶ N.289 (Moffett) 183; also see M. Henzelin, V. Heiskanen, G. Mettraux, Reparations To Victims Before The International Criminal Court: Lessons From International Mass Claims Processes, 17(3-4) *Criminal Law Forum* 2006, 317, 344

³⁶⁷ “The Human Rights Committee (CCPR), the Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (CESCR), Committee on the Elimination of Racial Discrimination (CERD), the Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW), Committee against Torture (CAT), Subcommittee on Prevention of Torture (SPT), Committee on the Rights of the Child (CRC), Committee on Migrant Workers (CMW), the Committee on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) and the Committee on Enforced Disappearances (CED)”: United Nations Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, Human Rights Bodies, 2015 <<http://www.ohchr.org/EN/HRBodies/Pages/HumanRightsBodies.aspx>> accessed 30th July 2015

³⁶⁸ N.211 (Kolb and Gaggioli) 443

³⁶⁹ Ibid

³⁷⁰ United Nations Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, Human Rights Bodies, 2015 <<http://www.ohchr.org/EN/HRBodies/Pages/HumanRightsBodies.aspx>> accessed 30th July 2015

³⁷¹ *Legal Consequences of the Construction of a Wall in the Occupied Palestinian Territory, Advisory Opinion* [2004] I.C.J. Rep., p.136, para.109; *Armed Activities on the Territory of the Congo (Democratic Republic of the Congo v Uganda)* [2005] I.C.J. Rep., p.168, paras.179-180; H. Keller, G. Ulfstein, L. Grover, *UN Human Rights Treaty Bodies: Law and Legitimacy* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press 2012) 54 & 358

³⁷² Ibid (Keller et al) 419

With most of the treaty bodies, victims and other states, can submit a complaint against a state (but not non-state actors) and only when the state has ratified an Optional Protocol.³⁷³

Non-governmental organisations, groups or individuals can send a complaint if they are victims or are privy to information about reliably evidenced and gross abuses of human rights and freedoms, so long as certain eligibility criteria are met.³⁷⁴ The treaty-bodies have acknowledged that IHR apply during NIACs and thereby create IHR duties to observe IHL, so long as IHL accords with IHR.³⁷⁵ However, they have been indisposed to deal with IHL matters, to scrutinise the core of the provisions and to explain how IHL and IHR apply concomitantly.³⁷⁶ This is because there is no treaty body for the Geneva Conventions.

Another issue is that there is a backlog of cases, it takes long to reach decisions due to the consensual decision-making process and decisions are non-binding.³⁷⁷ Also, the human rights treaty bodies are not an “exclusively...independent legal mechanism”.³⁷⁸ Hence, this mechanism is not like a court since some have governmental positions³⁷⁹ and not all its members are lawyers.³⁸⁰

3.2.5 The ICRC

³⁷³ N.211 (Kolb and Gaggioli) 448

³⁷⁴ Human Rights Council Resolution 5/1 (2007); United Nations Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, Human Rights Council Complaint Procedure, 2015
<<http://www.ohchr.org/EN/HRBodies/HRC/ComplaintProcedure/Pages/HRCCComplaintProcedureIndex.aspx>>
accessed 1st August 2015

³⁷⁵ N.211 (Kolb and Gaggioli) 448

³⁷⁶ Ibid

³⁷⁷ N.155 (Moeckli et al) 387

³⁷⁸ United Nations General Assembly, 62nd Session, Report of the Chairpersons of the Human Rights Treaty Bodies on Their Nineteenth Meeting - Effective Implementation of International Instruments on Human Rights, Including Reporting Obligations under International Instruments on Human Rights, 13 August 2007, UN Doc. A/52/224, para.8

³⁷⁹ N.371 (Keller et al) 404-405

³⁸⁰ Ibid, 405

The idea to send doctors to those who are wounded during conflicts was espoused by Dunant and led to the creation of the ICRC in 1864.³⁸¹ Religious and humanitarian motivation and the concept of charity played an important role in the formation of the ICRC.³⁸² The ICRC started its operational activities in 1870 and incrementally developed its activities.³⁸³ The First World War necessitated that the ICRC was put on a strong doctrinal basis rooted in the principles of impartiality, independence, universality and charity.³⁸⁴ The ICRC acted as a catalyst for the “International Red Cross Movement” and by 2006, this led to the establishment of 185 domestic Red Cross societies.³⁸⁵

The ICRC, as well the national societies, are authorised by virtue of the Geneva Conventions to encourage that IHL is being adhered to and to safeguard and help military and civilian victims during armed conflicts.³⁸⁶ It therefore develops IHL, issues standards of conduct, includes IHL into peace or ceasefire agreements, and provides training opportunities, including for opposition groups.³⁸⁷

Those states which have ratified the Geneva Conventions gain membership and participate together with members of the Red Crescent Movement and the International Red Cross in the

³⁸¹ M. Haas, *International Human Rights: A Comprehensive Introduction* (2nd ed, Abingdon, Routledge 2013) 67

³⁸² D. P. Forsythe, B. A. J. Rieffer-Flanagan, *The International Committee of the Red Cross, A neutral humanitarian actor* (Abingdon, Routledge 2007) 8

³⁸³ G. Willemin, R. Heacock, J. Freymond, *The International Committee of the Red Cross* (The Hague, Martinus Nijhoff Publishers 1984) 24

³⁸⁴ E. Wortel, Humanitarians and their moral stance in war: the underlying values, 91(876) *International Review of the Red Cross* 2009, 779-802, 784

³⁸⁵ N.382 (Forsythe and Rieffer-Flanagan) 1

³⁸⁶ Also see Article 5(2)(c)-(d) of the Statutes of the International Red Cross and Red Crescent Movement 1986; also see Regulation IV/3 adopted at the International Conferences on the Red Cross and Red Crescent in Berlin in 1869, as well as similar resolutions adopted in Berlin in 1869, Karlsruhe in 1887, in Washington in 1912, in Geneva in 1921 and in London in 1938; Reports and Documents, Action by the International Committee of the Red Cross in the vent of violations of international humanitarian law or of other fundamental rules protecting persons in situations of violence, 87(858) *International Review of the Red Cross* 2005, 393-400, 393

³⁸⁷ S. Herr, ‘Constraining the Conduct of Non-State Armed Groups’ in (eds) A. P. Jakobi, K. D. Wolf, *The Transnational Governance of Violence and Crime: Non-State Actors in Security* (Basingstoke, Palgrave MacMillan 2013) 47

International Conference of the Red Cross and Red Crescent.³⁸⁸ Since 1990, the ICRC has been afforded observer status by the UN.³⁸⁹

However, CA3 only provides that the ICRC “may offer its services” and Article 18 of Protocol II provides the same and accordingly state parties and opposition groups are not obligated to accept any such assistance.³⁹⁰ This reflects the concern that relief can be perceived as foreign intervention or this possibly happening, but relief is frequently particularly important during NIACs.³⁹¹ Hence, civilians have not got a right to humanitarian assistance, except when state parties withhold consent and they suffer undue hardship and this causes starvation.³⁹² Yet even in these circumstances, there is no effective process to implement and enforce the right.³⁹³ Resultantly, relief is often delayed or denied and even when parties consent, civilians may not be provided with this since relief personnel have insufficient access to particular areas and may be targeted.³⁹⁴

As traditionally the ICRC has been concerned with the promulgation of IHL,³⁹⁵ it appears to have adopted the view that when there is any conflict between IHL and IHR, the former

³⁸⁸ D. Casalin, C. Lamb, Participation of States in the International Conference of the Red Cross and Red Crescent and assemblies of other international organizations, 91(876) *International Review of the Red Cross* 2009, 733, 734

³⁸⁹ United Nations General Assembly Resolution A/Res/45/6 (1990); International Committee of the Red Cross, The ICRC is granted observer status at the United Nations, 31 December 1990
<<https://www.icrc.org/eng/resources/documents/misc/57jnwh.htm>> accessed 29th July 2015

³⁹⁰ C. Barrat, *Status of NGOs in International Humanitarian Law* (Leiden, Koninklijke Brill NV 2014) 168

³⁹¹ N.141 (Bothe et al) 799

³⁹² Article 18(2) Protocol II and Article 14 Protocol II; H. Spieker, Twenty-five Years after the Adoption of Additional Protocol II: Breakthrough or Failure of Humanitarian legal Protection?’ in n.22 (Fischer et al) 149-150

³⁹³ R. A. Stoffels, Legal regulation of humanitarian assistance in armed conflict: Achievements and gaps, 86(855) *International Committee of the Red Cross* 2004, 515, 544

³⁹⁴ Article 18(2) of Protocol II and Article 14 of Protocol II; n.392 (Spieker) 148-149

³⁹⁵ D. P. Forsythe, *The Humanitarians: The International Committee of the Red Cross* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press 2005) 260

constitutes the *lex specialis* in all situations.³⁹⁶ However, civilians would be better protected if a more differentiated approach was adopted. The ICRC does not establish any mechanism to ensure that civilians can assert their human or humanitarian rights, but only ameliorates their suffering. Relief depends on the ICRC having enough funds and states are not obligated to contribute any particular amount and the organisation is reliant on donations.³⁹⁷

Whilst the ICRC has encouraged opposition groups to enter into agreements or to unilaterally declare that they will adhere to IHL, Herr opines that these activities have not reduced the civilian suffering and do not generally result in more adherence to IHL.³⁹⁸ Furthermore, despite the ICRC being privy to many IHL and IHR violations, it cannot comment on these in order to preserve its impartiality.³⁹⁹

3.2.6 Truth commissions

Truth commissions have been created to assist the country with coming to terms with the atrocities.⁴⁰⁰ They ensure that the abuses become officially documented⁴⁰¹ and thereby reinforce accountability.⁴⁰² Whilst the reports are important, truth commissions are not equipped with powers to sentence individuals and/or groups or to require that reparation is made.⁴⁰³ However, the Truth and Reconciliation Commission for Peru created a program of

³⁹⁶ C. C. Eriksen, M. Emberland, *The New International Law: An Anthology* (Leiden, Koninklijke Brill NV 2010) 133

³⁹⁷ N.340 (Forsythe) 471

³⁹⁸ N.387 (Herr) 47

³⁹⁹ N.387 (Herr) 48

⁴⁰⁰ For instance, in relation to the NIAC in Sierra Leone, a Truth and Reconciliation Commission was set up by virtue of the Lomé Peace Agreement 1999: W. Schabas, *The Relationship Between Truth Commissions and International Courts: The Case of Sierra Leone*, 25(4) *Human Rights Quarterly* 4, 2003, 1035, 1035

⁴⁰¹ M. P. Scharf, *The Case for a Permanent International Truth Commission*, 7 *Duke Journal of Comparative International Law* 1996-1997, 375, 375

⁴⁰² M. C. Bassiouni, *Searching for Peace and Achieving Justice: The Need for Accountability*, 59(4) *Law and Contemporary Problems* 1996, 9-28, 9

⁴⁰³ N.401 (Scharf) 375

integral reparations, so that victims were recognised, for instance, through memorials and public gestures.⁴⁰⁴

Nonetheless, in many instances truth commissions have been used instead of criminal proceedings.⁴⁰⁵ Sometimes, they have been used in tandem with courts, for example, in Rwanda together with the local *gacaca* trials or in Sierra Leone in conjunction with the Special Court and there has been a move towards truth commissions being perceived as complementary to proceedings, for instance, in East Timor.⁴⁰⁶ Yet truth commissions cost money and use up funds which could have been used to prosecute perpetrators.⁴⁰⁷ Governments may also obstruct their work.⁴⁰⁸

3.3 Summary

The duty of states to safeguard civilians during NIACs has various defects and equally the international system has got its problems. Resultantly, civilians are frequently not afforded the rights which IHL and IHR proclaim.

⁴⁰⁴ L. J. Laplante, K. Theidon, *Truth with Consequences: Justice and Reparations in Post-Truth Commission Peru*, 29 *Human Rights Quarterly* 2007, 228, 234

⁴⁰⁵ A. Bisset, *Truth Commissions and Criminal Courts* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press 2012) 46

⁴⁰⁶ *Ibid*

⁴⁰⁷ W. A. Schabas, S. Darcy, *Truth Commissions and Courts: The Tension Between Criminal Justice and the Search for Truth* (Dordrecht, Kluwer Academic Publishers 2004) 84

⁴⁰⁸ B. G. Ramcharan, *International Law and Fact-Finding in the Field of Human Rights* (Leiden, Koninklijke Brill NV 2014) 195

Chapter 4: The importance of increasing legal protection for civilians during NIACs

4.0 Introduction

Civilians are not only insufficiently protected since the domestic and international mechanisms are weak, there exist other legal issues, which heighten their vulnerability.

4.1 Non-intervention and delays by the UNSC

The UNSC often fails to intervene since the permanent five members veto resolutions or threaten to do so, despite atrocities being committed.⁴⁰⁹ Indeed, members of the UNSC are not legally obligated to refrain from using the veto power in such circumstances and no liability is imposed on the UNSC for the failure to prevent internationally wrongful acts.⁴¹⁰ Such an approach accords with Article 2(7) of the UN Charter which affirms the principle of non-intervention, despite this arguably undermining comprehensive security.⁴¹¹ The Cold

⁴⁰⁹ P. Webb, Deadlock or Restraint? The Security Council Veto and the Use of Force in Syria, 19(3) *Journal of Conflict & Security Law* 2014, 471, 471

⁴¹⁰ Ibid

⁴¹¹ H. Nasu, Revisiting the Principle of Non-Intervention: A Structural Principle of International Law or a Political Obstacle to Regional Security in Asia? 3(1) *Asian Journal of International Law* 23, 25, 25; Y. Zewei, The Democracy and Legality Value in the International Community and the Principle of Non-Intervention,

War suppressed such “collective security action”, but even in a post-Cold War era, divisions still exist which prevent that the UNSC performs a broader security role.⁴¹² Strategic interests thus prevent that civilians are protected during many NIACs.⁴¹³

Between 1946 and 2008, Russia made most use of the veto power, followed by the US, Britain, France and China.⁴¹⁴ For instance, Russia and China have vetoed various resolutions on Syria, including that Syria is referred to the ICC.⁴¹⁵ The threat of a veto use may also result in inaction or limited measures, as happened in the case of Darfur due to China’s veto threat.⁴¹⁶ Furthermore, permanent members, such as China, may not cast a vote to protect their own interest, but this does not prevent that a resolution is adopted.⁴¹⁷ Civilians are also left unprotected because of delays, as illustrated in the case of Rwanda.⁴¹⁸ Yet when a veto immobilises action and the UNSC is not exercising its functions,⁴¹⁹ the UNGA can convene and make recommendations by virtue of the Uniting for Peace Resolution 1950.⁴²⁰ Whilst this

Chinese Journal of Law 2013 <http://en.cnki.com.cn/Article_en/CJFDTOTAL-DOUB201205010.htm> accessed 1st September 2015

⁴¹² R. Leo, S. Terlizzi, *The (D)Evolution of the Security Council: A three-part Case Study of the Post-Cold War Use of the Veto*, Proceedings of the National Conference of Undergraduate Research, University of Kentucky, 2014, 1077, 1077 <<http://www.ncurproceedings.org/ojs/index.php/NCUR2014/article/view/1086/592>> accessed 28th August 2015

⁴¹³ H. E. McKibben, *State Strategies in International Bargaining, Play by the Rules of Change Them?* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press 2015) 37

⁴¹⁴ Global Policy Forum, 2015 <<https://www.globalpolicy.org/component/content/article/102-tables-and-charts/32810-changing-patterns-in-the-use-of-the-veto-in-the-security-council.html>> accessed 3rd September 2015

⁴¹⁵ Reuters, Factbox: U.N. Security Council action on the Syrian conflict, 22 February 2014 <<http://www.reuters.com/article/2014/02/22/us-syria-crisis-un-resolutions-idUSBREA1L0RU20140222>> accessed 2nd September 2015; BBC, Russia and China veto UN move to refer Syria to ICC, 22 May 2014 <<http://www.bbc.com/news/world-middle-east-27514256>> accessed 27th August 2015

⁴¹⁶ A. Roberts, D. Zaum, *Selective Security: War and the United Nations Security Council Since 1945* (Abingdon, Routledge 2008) 13

⁴¹⁷ S. Zhao, *Chinese Foreign Policy: Pragmatism and Strategic Behavior* (New York, East Gate Book 2004) 62

⁴¹⁸ A. de Hoogh, *Obligations Erga omnes and International Crimes: A Theoretical Inquiry into the Implementation and Enforcement of the International Responsibility of States* (The Hague, Kluwer Law International 1996) 405; D. Kuwali, *The Responsibility to Protect: Implementation of Article 4(h) Intervention* (Brill, Koninklijke Brill NV 2011) 355

⁴¹⁹ Cf Article 12(1) of the UN Charter

⁴²⁰ Articles 14 and 96(1) of the UN Charter; UNGA Resolution 377A (V) of 3 November 1950; n.13 (Summers) 226

resolution was utilised several times,⁴²¹ its effectiveness is limited since UNGA sanctioned military measures have no legal effect.⁴²²

Moreover, the veto power makes it possible that even non-derogable *jus cogens* which amount to “*obligatio erga omnes*” can be circumvented.⁴²³ Yet the UNSC is only entrusted with the maintenance of international peace and security and arguably has no responsibility to protect, also because this may cause division which undermines international peace and security.⁴²⁴ UNSC members do not hold the same opinion and no institutional mechanisms exist to consistently protect civilians from serious atrocities.⁴²⁵ Resultantly, the concept of responsibility to protect and humanitarian intervention is not as popular in practice as in theory.⁴²⁶ Nonetheless, the responsibility to protect principle has become more accepted in order to avert mass atrocities, for instance, UNSCR 1973 (2011) authorised “all necessary measures” to safeguard civilians in Libya, including a no-fly zone.⁴²⁷ Equally, the UNSC authorised force for civilian protection purposes in the case of Cote d'Ivoire.⁴²⁸

⁴²¹ N.416 (Roberts and Zaum) 13

⁴²² A. Narlikar, *Deadlocks in Multilateral Negotiations: Causes and Solutions* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press 2010) 192

⁴²³ M. C. Bassiouni, *International Crimes: Jus cogens and Obligatio Erga omnes*, 58(4) *Law and Contemporary Problems* 1996, 63, 63

⁴²⁴ H. Nasu, ‘The UN Security Council's Responsibility and the "Responsibility to Protect"’ in (eds) A. von Bogdandy, R. Wolfrum, *Max Planck Yearbook of United Nations Law, Volume 15, 2011* (Leiden, Koninklijke Brill NV 2011) 377-418, 377-378

⁴²⁵ *Ibid* (Nasu) 417-418

⁴²⁶ S. Chesterman, ‘Leading from Behind’: The Responsibility to Protect, the Obama Doctrine, and Humanitarian Intervention after Libya, 25(3) *Ethics & International Affairs* 2011, 279, 279

⁴²⁷ UNSC 1973 (2011), para.4; A. J. Bellamy, *Libya and the Responsibility to Protect: The Exception and the Norm*, 25(3) *Ethics & International Affairs* 2011, 263, 263

⁴²⁸ UNSCR 1528 (2004); UNSCR 1739 (2007); UNSCR 1933 (2010); UNSCR 1962 (2010); UNSCR 1967 (2011); UNSCR 1968 (2011); A. J. Bellamy, *ibid* (Williams) 825; A. Tzanakopoulos, *The UN/French Use of Force in Abidjan: Uncertainties Regarding the Scope of UN Authorizations*, Blog of the European Journal of International Law, 9 April 2011 <<http://www.ejiltalk.org/the-un-use-of-force-in-abidjan/>> accessed 25th August 2015

Furthermore, the role of the Special Adviser on the Prevention of Genocide⁴²⁹ became extended in 2007, when the Joint Office of the Special Adviser on the Prevention of Genocide and on the Responsibility to Protect was created.⁴³⁰

Nevertheless, the use of force regime created after WWII has not evolved together with the idea of IHR and this lack of a normative framework for humanitarian intervention leaves civilians unprotected.⁴³¹

4.2 Impunity issues for peacekeeping and UN authorised troops

The UN is not a party to the Geneva Conventions or to international or regional human rights treaties.⁴³² In law, their conduct is thus not regulated by them and responsibility cannot be established, e.g., through the treaties' complaint mechanisms.⁴³³ Whilst it is generally accepted that they are bound by customary law applies, the precise parameters are unclear because arguably this requires that *opinio juris* and institutional practice has to be shown to exist in relation to every customary rule.⁴³⁴ However, the International Law Commission has prepared draft articles on the responsibility of international organisations.⁴³⁵

Moreover, the ECtHR has found that the acts of Kosovo forces (KFOR) and those by the UN Mission in Kosovo (UNMIK) were attributable to the UN since the UNSC had authorised

⁴²⁹ UNSCR 1366 (2001)

⁴³⁰ International Coalition for the Responsibility to Protect, Joint Office of the Special Adviser on the Prevention of Genocide and on the Responsibility to Protect, 2015

<<http://responsibilitytoprotect.org/index.php/component/content/article/3618>> accessed 26th August 2015; n.427 (Bellamy) 263

⁴³¹ C. Burke, Symposium: Live & Let Die: Can Political Indifference to Mass Atrocity be overcome by Law or Responsibility to Protect? An Essay on Fighting with One Arm Tied Behind One's Back, or: The Responsibility to Protect, General Principles and the Future of Humanitarian Intervention, 23 *Michigan State University Journal of International Law* 2015, 635, 635

⁴³² N. D. White, *The Law of International Organisations* (2nd ed, Manchester, Manchester University Press 2005) 24

⁴³³ K. M. Larsen, *The Human Rights Treaty Obligations of Peacekeepers* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press 2012) 12

⁴³⁴ G. Verdirame, *The UN and Human Rights: Who Guards the Guardians?* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press 2011) 56; M. C. Zwanenburg, *Accountability Of Peace Support Operations* (Leiden, Koninklijke Brill NV 2005) 131

⁴³⁵ International Law Commission, Draft Articles on the Responsibility of International Organisations, UN Doc. 1/59/10, 99; L. B. De Chazournes, M. G. Kohen, *International Law and the Quest for Its Implementation: Liber Amicorum Vera Gowlland-Debbas* (Leiden, Koninklijke Brill NV 2010) 52

force and created the UNMIK by virtue of its Chapter VII powers.⁴³⁶ Yet the ECtHR ruled that this link was insufficient to establish a link to the states and it therefore declined jurisdiction.⁴³⁷ In light of the fact that multiple or dual attribution is likely to occur, direct accountability of states and indirect accountability of international organisations is substantially weakened by this decision.⁴³⁸ This is because UN peacekeepers are provided by member states, but for many years there have been reports about human rights abuses by those, who are meant to protect civilians.⁴³⁹ Yet when the UNSC creates a UN peacekeeping mission, the member states, which contribute troops, will be provided with specific guidelines and these guidelines require that military peacekeepers receive training, including about the prohibition against sexual abuse.⁴⁴⁰ UN Secretary Annan also published a bulletin which calls on peacekeepers to observe IHL.⁴⁴¹ Despite this, in August of this year new allegations of sex abuse by peacekeepers in the Central African Republic surfaced, highlighting the still existing impunity which deprives civilians of their rights under IHL and IHR.⁴⁴²

Moreover, Articles 104 and 105 of the UN Charter confers functional immunity on the UN and whilst the UNGA can recommend how this should be applied or can propose

⁴³⁶ *Behrami v France and Saramati v France, Germany and Norway*, Application No. 71412/01 and Application No. 78166/01, 2 March 2007; L. Clarke, *Public-Private Partnerships and Responsibility Under International Law: A Global Health Perspective* (Abingdon, Routledge 2014) 164-165

⁴³⁷ *Behrami v France and Saramati v France, Germany and Norway*, Application No. 71412/01 and Application No. 78166/01, 2 March 2007, paras. 144, 149, 151-152; also see *Kasumaj v Greece*, Application No. 6974/04, ECtHR, 5 July 2007

⁴³⁸ N.434 (Verdirame) 56; n.434 (Zwanenburg) 113

⁴³⁹ F. Lewis, Human Rights Abuses in UN Peacekeeping: Providing Redress and Punishment while continuing Peacekeeping Missions for Humanitarian Progress, 23 *Southern California Interdisciplinary Law Journal* 2014, 595, 596

⁴⁴⁰ B. Oswald, H. Durham, A. Bates, *Documents on the Law of UN Peace Operations* (Oxford, Oxford University Press 2010) 529-530

⁴⁴¹ United Nations Secretary General, ST/SGB/1999/13: Observance by United Nations Forces of International Humanitarian Law; M. Weller, *The Oxford Handbook of the Use of Force in International Law* (Oxford, Oxford University Press 2015) 432

⁴⁴² J. Mariner, UN peacekeepers who rape and abuse are criminals - so treat them as such, *The Guardian*, 20 August 2015 <<http://www.theguardian.com/global-development/2015/aug/20/un-peacekeepers-rape-sexual-abuse-criminals-car-ban-ki-moon>> accessed 2nd September 2015

conventions, this immunity has been extended to peacekeeping operations and the personnel since they are a subsidiary body.⁴⁴³ Hence, there exists an “accountability gap in peacekeeping” and civilians cannot hold peacekeepers responsible for grave IHR breaches.⁴⁴⁴ Furthermore, peacekeeping troops have evoked the concept of self-defence, but this has made it extremely difficult to distinguish it from the use of force, especially when “robust UN peacekeeping” has been authorised, as happened, for instance, in Liberia.⁴⁴⁵ It also leaves unanswered the question whether they can only use self-defence or turn into peace enforcers and renders it difficult to distinguish peacekeepers from war fighters.⁴⁴⁶ Recently, there has been a move towards more aggressive peacekeeping by requiring “neutralisation” of armed rebel groups.⁴⁴⁷ The Brahimi Report cautioned against this since it erodes the neutrality of UN peacekeepers.⁴⁴⁸ Lack of independence makes it more difficult to obtain consent from all parties to the conflict, but this is needed since peacekeeping missions have no basis in the UN Charter.⁴⁴⁹ Hence, authorisation of aggressive/robust peacekeeping can in turn adversely affect civilians.⁴⁵⁰ For instance, delays can arise, as happened when UNSCR 1291 (2000) was adopted and which required credible guarantees from all those named in the Lusaka Ceasefire Agreement.⁴⁵¹ Consent can also be renounced.⁴⁵²

⁴⁴³ Article 105(3) of the UN Charter; R. S. Burke, *Sexual Exploitation and Abuse by UN Military Contingents: Moving Beyond the Current Status Quo and Responsibility under International Law* (Leiden, Koninklijke Brill NV 2014) 85

⁴⁴⁴ H. Krieger, Peacekeeping: Law-Making by Domestic Courts As a Way to Avoid UN Reform? 62(2) *Netherlands International Law Review* 2015, 259, 259

⁴⁴⁵ UNSCR 1509 (2003); n.441 (Weller) 365-366

⁴⁴⁶ N. D. White, C. Henderson, *Research Handbook on International Conflict and Security Law* (Cheltenham, Edward Elgar Publishing Ltd 2013) 585- 586

⁴⁴⁷ See for example, United Nations Security Council Resolution 2098 (2013) on the Democratic Republic of the Congo, para. 12(b); D. Whittle, Peacekeeping in Conflict: The Intervention Brigade, MONUSCO, and the Application of International Humanitarian Law to United Nations Forces, 46 *Georgetown Journal of International Law* 2014-2015, 837, 837; also see F. K. Nkusi, Legal Implications of Shifting Paradigm: Intervention Brigade - MONUSCO's Enforcement Action in the DRC, 2(2) *Berkeley Journal of International Law* 2013, 1, 7

⁴⁴⁸ G. Wilson, *The United Nations and Collective Security* (Abingdon, Routledge 2014) 137

⁴⁴⁹ H. Nasu, *International Law on Peacekeeping: A Study of Article 40 of the UN Charter* (Leiden, Koninklijke Brill NB 2009) 22

⁴⁵⁰ N.446 (Whittle) 837

⁴⁵¹ *Ibid* 300

Another problem with ensuring that civilians are protected is that the UN depends on states to pay for peacekeeping operations, but by 30 April 2015, \$1.9 billion of the \$8.47 billion approved resources for 2014 to 2015 were outstanding,⁴⁵³ with France owing the most, followed by the US.⁴⁵⁴

4.3 Issues with establishing universal jurisdiction for grave breaches under the Geneva Conventions and customary law

In respect of IACs, the Geneva Conventions provide that states should try those who have committed grave breaches in their courts.⁴⁵⁵ Universal jurisdiction enables the ICC or third party states to prosecute war crimes, genocide or crimes against humanity,⁴⁵⁶ as well as crimes set out in the UN Torture Convention⁴⁵⁷ and in the ICC statute.⁴⁵⁸

State and ICC practice supports that the Conventions give rise to universal jurisdiction and it has been argued that this is a customary rule which also binds those, who are not party to the Geneva Conventions.⁴⁵⁹ However, in respect of crimes which do not breach CA3, but are committed during NIACs, Article 6 of Protocol II allows for penal prosecution, though is not explicit about its territorial reach.⁴⁶⁰ Universal jurisdiction is thus not mandatory when grave

⁴⁵² C. D. Gray, *International Law and the Use of Force* (3rd ed, Oxford, Oxford University Press 2008) 299-300

⁴⁵³ United Nations Peacekeeping, Peacekeeping Fact Sheet, 30 April 2015

<<http://www.un.org/en/peacekeeping/resources/statistics/factsheet.shtml>> accessed 25th July 2015

⁴⁵⁴ Guardian, Member states owe UN \$3.5bn, 10 October 2014

<<http://www.theguardian.com/world/2014/oct/10/un-member-states-owe-debt>> accessed 25th July 2015

⁴⁵⁵ Articles 49-50, 129 and 146 of the four Geneva Conventions and Article 85(1) of Protocol I to the Geneva Conventions; C. Ryngaert, *Jurisdiction in International Law* (Oxford, Oxford University Press 2008) 111

⁴⁵⁶ M. Langer, *The Archipelago and the Wheel. The Universal Jurisdiction and the International Criminal Court Regimes*, University of California, 2011, 1, 1 <http://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=1942625> accessed 1st September 2015

⁴⁵⁷ Article 5(2) of the Convention against Torture and other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment 1984

⁴⁵⁸ N.455 (Ryngaert) 111

⁴⁵⁹ Also see UN Commission on Human Rights, Resolution 1999/1, 16th meeting, 6 April 1999

⁴⁶⁰ N.455 (Ryngaert) 111

breaches are committed during NIACs.⁴⁶¹ However, the ICTY has made clear that universal jurisdiction can apply when war crimes are committed during NIACs, though tribunals like the ICTY have not been set up for every internal conflict.⁴⁶²

Furthermore, the success of the universal jurisdiction is highlighted by the prosecution of the first head of state - Charles Taylor, the ex-president of Liberia - by the UN based Special Court for Sierra Leone.⁴⁶³ Yet the doctrine of “head of state immunity” undermines the universal jurisdiction doctrine.⁴⁶⁴

Furthermore, individual states have very rarely supplemented the ICC and cooperated with it in order to increase investigations and prosecutions.⁴⁶⁵ Many dualist states have neglected to adopt domestic legislation for grave breaches, without which the universal jurisdiction doctrine is meaningless.⁴⁶⁶ Moreover, critics observe that such a decentralised regime creates judicial chaos, disturbs international relations and undermines political answers in respect of mass atrocities.⁴⁶⁷ The prosecution of perpetrators by states is also fraught with legal and practical problems.⁴⁶⁸ Unaffected states may lack the motivation to pursue perpetrators.⁴⁶⁹

4.4 Amnesties for those taking part in NIACs

⁴⁶¹ *Prosecutor v Tadic*, Case No. IT-94-1-AR72, Appeals Chamber, Decision on the Defence Motion for Interlocutory Appeal on Jurisdiction, 2 October 1995, para.80; n.157 (Ambach et al) 258

⁴⁶² *Ibid* (*Prosecutor v Tadic*); *ibid* (Ambach et al) 258

⁴⁶³ B. Thompson, Universal Criminal Jurisdiction: Law and Practice in Sierra Leone, 3 *International Criminal Justice Series* 2015, 75, 75

⁴⁶⁴ B. M.-H. Chok, The Struggle Between the Doctrines of Universal Jurisdiction and Head of State Immunity, 20 *University of California, Davis, Journal of International Law* 2013-2014, 233, 233

⁴⁶⁵ N.456 (Langer) 1

⁴⁶⁶ K. Dormann, R. Geiss, The Implementation of Grave Breaches into Domestic Legal Orders, 7(4) *Journal of International Criminal Justice* 2009, 703-721, 703; R. Lemaître, Belgium rules the world*: Universal Jurisdiction over Human Rights Atrocities, 27(2) *Jura Falconis* 2000-2001, 255, 282
<<https://www.law.kuleuven.be/jura/art/37n2/lemaitre.htm>> accessed 1st September 2015

⁴⁶⁷ M. Langer, The Diplomacy of Universal Jurisdiction: The Political Branches and the Transnational Prosecution of International Crimes, 105(1) *The American Journal of International Law* 2011, 1, 49; S. Yee, Universal Jurisdiction: Concept, Logic, and Reality, 10(3) *Chinese Journal of International Law* 2011, 503, 503

⁴⁶⁸ H. van der Wilt, ‘Sadder but Wiser’? NGOs and Universal Jurisdiction for International Crimes, 13(2) *Journal of International Criminal Justice* 2015, 313, 313

⁴⁶⁹ *Ibid*, 315

Civilians are also unprotected since Protocol II states that “the authorities...shall endeavour to grant the broadest possible amnesty” in respect of the various acts which are listed as being prohibited and requiring prosecution.⁴⁷⁰ Amnesties result in wrongdoing not being punished.⁴⁷¹

National courts have relied on this provision in order to grant amnesties even for war crimes.⁴⁷² However, this puts in doubt the *erga omnes* obligation to charge and sentence perpetrators of international crimes which constitute *jus cogens*.⁴⁷³

The Rome Statute does not mention amnesties and this causes ambiguity since it is unclear whether national laws prevent the court from having jurisdiction.⁴⁷⁴ However, Hafner et al observe that in respect of crimes which fall within the ICC’s jurisdiction no amnesties can be granted.⁴⁷⁵ Yet amnesties can be granted by the UNSC and so prevent that the ICC deals with a case.⁴⁷⁶ Furthermore, when a state investigates or prosecutes the person, then ICC action is precluded since the ICC’s jurisdiction is complementary.⁴⁷⁷ Equally, the *ne bis in idem*

⁴⁷⁰ C. Murungu, J. Biegon, *Prosecuting International Crimes in Africa* (Pretoria, Pretoria University Law Press 2011) 30

⁴⁷¹ L. Mallinder, K. McEvoy, Rethinking amnesties: atrocity, accountability and impunity in post-conflict societies, 6(1) *Contemporary Social Science: Journal of the Academy of Social Sciences* 2011, 107, 128

⁴⁷² *Romo Mena Case*, Corte Suprema de Chile, 26 October 1995; *Azanian Peoples Organization and ors v President of South Africa and ors*, Constitutional Court (South Africa), No.CCT 17/96, 1996 (4) SA 671 (CC), I.L.D.C. 648 (1996); n.170 (Weatherall) 328; F. Z. Ntoubandi, *Amnesty for Crimes Against Humanity Under International Law* (Leiden, Koninklijke Brill NV 2007) 223

⁴⁷³ P. A. Schey, D. L. Shelton, N. Roht-Arriaza, Addressing human rights abuses: Truth commissions and the value of amnesty, 19 *Whittier Law Review* 1997, 325, 325 ; n.474 (Murungu and Biegon) 30; n.170 (Weatherall) 329

⁴⁷⁴ N. Szablewska, S.-D. Bachmann, *Current Issues in Transitional Justice: Towards a More Holistic Approach* (London, Springer 2015) 39

⁴⁷⁵ G. Hafner, K. Boon, A. Rubesame, J. Huston, A Response to the American View as presented by Ruth Wedgewood, 10 *European Journal of International Law* 1999, 108, 111

⁴⁷⁶ Article 16 of the Rome Statute; see for example, UNSCR 1422 (2002); D. Campbell, *A Bird in the Bush: Failed Policies of the George W. Bush Administration* (New York, Algora Publishing 2005) 146; also see C. Stahn, The Ambiguities of Security Council Resolution 1422 (2002), 14(1) *European Journal of International Law* 2003, 85, 85

⁴⁷⁷ Article 17 of the Rome Statute; S. B. Sewall, C. Kaysen, *The United States and the International Criminal Court, National Security and International Law* (Oxford, Rowman & Littlefield Publishers Inc 2000) 188; M. Politi, F. Gioia, *The International Criminal Court and National Jurisdictions* (Aldershot, Ashgate Publishing Ltd 2008) 15

doctrine prevents ICC action since it proscribes that an accused is convicted for something for which he already provided a confession and received penalties.⁴⁷⁸

Moreover, it has been argued that agreements which try and bestow such amnesties are void since they derogate from established peremptory norms.⁴⁷⁹ This is underscored by the Convention on the Prevention and Punishment of the Crime of Genocide 1948 and the Convention against Torture, and Other Cruel, Inhumane or Degrading Treatment or Punishment 1984 which contain provisions mandating prosecution and punishment.⁴⁸⁰ Yet state practice is rather mixed and between 1999 and 2007, 28 amnesty laws did not exclude international crimes, whereas 34 others did.⁴⁸¹ This illustrates that it is not yet clear in respect of which crimes amnesties can be granted.

Yet even when a prosecution policy has been included, this is typically limited to a small group of high-ranking perpetrators, whereas lower ranks and their promoters avoid legal accountability.⁴⁸² Hence, the issue is that amnesties promote impunity, but without amnesties post-conflict restorative and transitional justice objectives may be hampered and more civilians may be harmed.⁴⁸³

4.5 Establishing liability for breaches of IHL and IHR

⁴⁷⁸ Article 20 of the Rome Statute; *ibid* (Sewall and Kaysen)

⁴⁷⁹ Article 53 of the VCLT; n.472 (Ntoubandi) 24

⁴⁸⁰ R. Jeffery, *Amnesties, Accountability, and Human Rights* (Pennsylvania, Pennsylvania Press 2014) 28

⁴⁸¹ A. Novak, *Comparative Executive Clemency: The Constitutional Pardon Power and the Prerogative of Mercy in Global Perspective* (Abingdon, Routledge 2016) 55

⁴⁸² F. Lessa, L. A. Payne, *Amnesty in the Age of Human Rights Accountability: Comparative and International Perspectives* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press 2012) 94

⁴⁸³ *Ibid*; K. McEvoy, L. Mallinder, Amnesties in Transition: Punishment, Restoration, and the Governance of Mercy, 39(3) *Journal of Law and Society* 2012, 410, 410

Civilians are unprotected since the rights contained in CA3 and Protocol II are unenforceable in domestic courts since these provisions are silent about prosecuting perpetrators.⁴⁸⁴ Only if national penal and military laws are enacted will liability be established.⁴⁸⁵ Whilst the treaty provisions can be evoked in monist countries without the adoption of national implementing legislation, this is not the case in dualist countries.⁴⁸⁶ However, states cannot rely on their domestic law to justify their failure to discharge their treaty obligations.⁴⁸⁷ Accordingly, “[o]nce it is recognised that obligations are owed to individuals..[i]t becomes unsustainable to regard the treatment of one's own nationals as matters falling essentially within domestic jurisdiction...”⁴⁸⁸ Yet CA3 and Protocol II do not specifically mandate that individuals are prosecuted or spell out enforcement mechanisms.⁴⁸⁹

In terms of IHR, the situation is slightly different. Article 2 of the ICCPR provides that contracting states have to enforce the respective rights or adopt legislation to that effect and Article 2(3) explicates that this necessitates an effective remedy.⁴⁹⁰ This means that domestic human rights institutions have to be created.⁴⁹¹ In respect of the ICESCR, the requirement is different and a state has to discharge the duties “to the maximum of its available

⁴⁸⁴ T. Graditzky, Individual criminal responsibility for violations of international humanitarian law committed in NIACs, *International Review of the Red Cross*, No. 322, 31 March 1998

<<https://www.icrc.org/eng/resources/documents/misc/57jp4l.htm>> accessed 1st September 2015

⁴⁸⁵ International Committee of the Red Cross, National Enforcement, International Humanitarian Law. Information Kit, 2004, 1, 4 <https://www.icrc.org/eng/assets/files/other/kit_national_enforcement.pdf> accessed 4th September 2015

⁴⁸⁶ B. Marian, The Dualist and Monist Theories: International Law's Comprehension, University of Targu-Mures, 2007, 1, 2-4 <http://revcurentjur.ro/arhiva/attachments_200712/recjurid071_22F.pdf> accessed 2nd September 2015

⁴⁸⁷ Article 27 of the VCLT; n.193 (Evans) 41

⁴⁸⁸ R. Higgins, *Problems and Process, International Law and How We Use It* (Oxford, Clarendon Press 1995) 95-97

⁴⁸⁹ D. L. DeLaet, *The Global Struggle for Human Rights* (2nd ed, Boston, Cengage Learning 2014) 38; n.484 (Graditzky)

⁴⁹⁰ L. C. Reif, *The Ombudsman, Good Governance and the International Human Rights System* (Leiden, Koninklijke Brill NV 2004) 121

⁴⁹¹ See for example Human Rights Committee - Concluding Observations: Togo, UN Doc. CCPR/CO/76/TGO (28 November 2002) para.8; *ibid* (Reif) 121

resources.”⁴⁹² Hence, the rights are dependent on the “macroeconomic reality.”⁴⁹³ The enforcement of ICESC rights is therefore more elusive than real since civil wars often destroy societal institutions and frequently occur in poverty-stricken countries.⁴⁹⁴

However, in comparison to IHL for which there are no specific courts to which civilians can apply to, IHR are more enforceable in countries which have acceded to regional human rights treaties, such as the ECHR and the ACHPR.⁴⁹⁵ The European Commission has stated that military operations have to be planned “where the use of force is envisaged in the vicinity of the civilian population, with regard to the avoidance of incidental loss of life and injury to others”.⁴⁹⁶ The ECtHR has implicitly enforced IHL by finding that not enough had been done to avoid that civilian losses are minimised and that knowledge about the killing triggered a duty to conduct an investigation.⁴⁹⁷ In another case, the ECtHR again employed IHL language when enquiring whether civilian loss could have been minimised.⁴⁹⁸ Nonetheless, regional human rights courts are not available in many countries and civilians cannot apply to any international courts, as mentioned above. Most fundamentally, the ICC’s jurisdiction is limited to “genocide, crimes against humanity, war crimes and the crime of aggression”.⁴⁹⁹ The jurisdiction of the ICTY is similarly worded⁵⁰⁰ and the jurisdiction of the ICTR is

⁴⁹² F. Coomans, M. T. Kamminga, *Extraterritorial Application of Human Rights Treaties* (Oxford, Intersentia 2004) 222

⁴⁹³ M. Dowell-Jones, *Contextualising The International Covenant On Economic, Social And Cultural Rights: Assessing the Economic Deficit* (Leiden, Koninklijke Brill NV 2004) 40

⁴⁹⁴ E. Newman, *A Crisis of Global Institutions?: Multilateralism and International Security* (Abingdon, Routledge 2007) 95; A. Misra, *Politics of Civil Wars: Conflict, Intervention & Resolution* (Abingdon, Routledge 2008) 18

⁴⁹⁵ N.111 (Clapham and Gaeta) 412

⁴⁹⁶ *Ergy v Turkey*, Commission Report, 20 May 1997, para.145; n.64 (Perna) 88

⁴⁹⁷ *Ergi v Turkey* [1998] E.C.H.R. 59, paras79&85; *ibid* (Perna) 88

⁴⁹⁸ *Isayeva v Russia* [2005] 41 E.C.H.R. 38; M. Forowicz, *The Reception of International Law in the European Court of Human Rights* (Oxford, Oxford University Press 2010) 332

⁴⁹⁹ Article 5 of the Rome Statute; O. A. Maunganidze, *Power and Prosecution - Pouvoir Et Poursuite: Challenges and Opportunities for International Criminal Justice in Sub-Saharan Africa* (Gottingen, Universitätsverlag Gottingen 2012) 64

⁵⁰⁰ Articles 2-5 of the Statute of the ICTY

curtailed to “genocide”, “crimes against humanity”, “violations of common Article 3...and Additional Protocol II.”⁵⁰¹ Hence, none of these international venues prosecute pure IHR breaches.

Furthermore, prosecutions at the ICTY, ICTR and the ICC have been often very slow, but delays can prevent successful prosecutions.⁵⁰² Hybrid courts, as e.g., were created for Cambodia and Sierra Leone, have not been established consistently in respect of all armed conflicts and have their own flaws.⁵⁰³ For example, like the ICC, the ICTY has been accused of being “a political court” which ignored the war crimes committed by NATO.⁵⁰⁴

The operational costs for the ICC are also prohibitive: By 2012, it had nearly cost \$1bn,⁵⁰⁵ despite the ICC having only dealt with 22 cases by 2015.⁵⁰⁶

4.6 Other reasons for increasing legal protection

The existing mechanisms to protect civilians are nascent. Insufficient attention is paid to environmental protection during NIACs and no liability is imposed for harm occasioned.⁵⁰⁷

International environmental law has not been treated as the *lex specialis* for IHL, despite the fact that harm to the environment can have catastrophic consequences for civilians.⁵⁰⁸ The

⁵⁰¹ Articles 2-4 of the Statute of the ICTR; A. Del Vecchio, *New International Tribunals and New International Proceedings* (Giuffrè, Rome 2006) 121

⁵⁰² A. Whiting, In International Criminal Prosecutions, Justice Delayed Can Be Justice Delivered, 50(2) *Harvard International Law Journal* 2009, 323, 363

⁵⁰³ A. Fichtelberg, *Hybrid Tribunals: A Comparative Examination* (London, Springer 2015) 104

⁵⁰⁴ J. N. Clark, *Serbia in the Shadow of Milosevic: The Legacy of Conflict in the Balkans* (London, IB Tauris & Co Ltd 2008) 107

⁵⁰⁵ J. Silverman, Ten years, \$900m, one verdict: Does the ICC cost too much? BBC, 14 March 2012 <<http://www.bbc.com/news/magazine-17351946>> accessed 3rd September 2015

⁵⁰⁶ International Criminal Court, Situations and cases, 2015 <http://www.icc-cpi.int/en_menus/icc/situations%20and%20cases/Pages/situations%20and%20cases.aspx> accessed 2nd September 2015

⁵⁰⁷ I. Lechtimiakytė, Preservation of Environment in Times of NIAC, Legal Framework, Its Sufficiency and Suggestions, 20(2) *Jurisprudence* 2013, 569, 569 <<https://www.mruni.eu/upload/iblock/15d/JUR-13-20-2-11.pdf>> accessed 3rd September 2015

⁵⁰⁸ N.17 (Sivakumaran) 526

law is thus undeveloped, lacks measures to realise compliance and redress the impact of environmental violations.⁵⁰⁹

Moreover, whilst during IACs, the International Humanitarian Fact-Finding Commission can be requested to investigate facts independently, this option does not exist in respect of NIACs.⁵¹⁰ Whilst to a certain extent, this mechanism has become replaced by the Human Rights Council, the issue is that this latter body is not impartial or independent, but is a political body composed not only of human rights proponents, but also states which are known “human rights offenders.”⁵¹¹ Also, fact-finding missions and missions of inquiry by the Human Rights Council have had a limited impact.⁵¹²

There thus exist no automatic process to gather evidence whilst the conflict is taking place, which can be used for military and criminal prosecutions, whether domestically, in third party countries, regional courts, at hybrid tribunals or the ICC.⁵¹³ NGOs frequently have insufficient staff to conduct comprehensive monitoring and cannot protect local sources and their information must be made public, but to gain attention, accounts may be exaggerated.⁵¹⁴ No independent external monitoring mechanism exists, which facilitate that all who are engaged in the fighting and those who support the different parties can be held responsible.⁵¹⁵ Hence, military operations are insufficiently controlled and whilst the media and NGOs play an important role, this is insufficient to accurately alert the public about abuse against

⁵⁰⁹ C. McKay, Protecting the Silent Victim from Irregular Actors: Improving Non-State Compliance with the International Law of Environmental Protection in Armed Conflict, Australian National University College of Law Research Paper No.12-18, 2012, 1, 39 <http://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2082599> accessed 1st September 2015

⁵¹⁰ Article 90 of Protocol II

⁵¹¹ H. Krieger, *Inducing Compliance with International Humanitarian Law: Lessons from the African Great Lakes Region* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press 2015) 266

⁵¹² N.129 (Oberleitner) 321

⁵¹³ N.64 (Perna) 95

⁵¹⁴ Ibid, 95-96

⁵¹⁵ N.17 (Sivakumaran) 566

civilians.⁵¹⁶ The lack of an effective monitoring mechanism (i.e. systematic gathering and analysis of data about IHR and IHL breaches), fact-finding missions (i.e. investigation of breaches) and a reporting process (i.e. the processing of the data in reports) make it easier for the warring parties to not comply with IHR and IHL norms.⁵¹⁷ Civilian casualty tracking should become a customary practice, as for instance, was used by NATO's International Security Assistance Force in Afghanistan since 2008.⁵¹⁸

Most fundamentally, the current regime places too much emphasis on repressing those who breach IHR and IHL, instead of focusing on prevention,⁵¹⁹ for instance, through “early warning, mediation, confidence building measures, fact-finding, preventive deployment, and peace zones”, as well as “policies that address the institutional, socio-economic, and global environment.”⁵²⁰

4.7 Summary

It has been shown that it is crucial to increase protection for civilians during NIACs since the existing regimes suffer from many weaknesses, ranging from inaction of the UNSC to issues with establishing liability for breaches of IHL and IHR.

⁵¹⁶ D. Fleck, ‘International humanitarian law after September 11: challenges and the need to respond’ in (eds) T. McCormack, A. McDonald, *Yearbook of International Humanitarian Law - 2003, Volume 6; Volume 2003* (The Hague, TMC Asser Press 2006) 68

⁵¹⁷ P. Bongard, J. Somer, Monitoring armed non-state actor compliance with humanitarian norms: a look at international mechanisms and the Geneva Call Deed of Commitment, 93(883) *International Review of the Red Cross* 2011, 673, 675

⁵¹⁸ Center for Civilians in Conflict, *Civilian Harm Tracking: Analysis of ISAF Efforts in Afghanistan*, Washington DC, 2014, 1, 1

<http://civiliansinconflict.org/uploads/files/publications/ISAF_Civilian_Harm_Tracking.pdf> accessed 2nd September 2015

⁵¹⁹ N.392 (Spieker) 129, 165; n.17 (Sivakumaran) 83

⁵²⁰ O. T. Ganiyu, Preventing Interstate Armed Conflict: Whose responsibility? *Jonkoping International Business School*, 2010, 1, 17-18 <<http://hj.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:381932/FULLTEXT02.pdf>> accessed 2nd September 2015

Conclusion

The legal regime for NIACs based on CA3, Protocol II, IHR customary law and international law insufficiently protects civilians. The rights which civilians should in theory be afforded during NIACs are extremely difficult to enforce and to protect due to the intentional legal loopholes, which safeguard the sovereignty of states and international power politics.

The requirements to establish a NIAC in Protocol II are too difficult to satisfy. This results in countries being able to forego the strictures of Protocol II. Equally, the way in which combatants and civilians and those, who should be protected, have been defined creates uncertainty. The treaty articles afford too little protective safeguards to civilians and the existence of customary IHL for NIACs is controversial.⁵²¹

Whilst the main sources for IHL are the four Geneva Conventions and their two Protocols,⁵²² civilians during NIACs cannot evoke Convention IV or Protocol I, which particularly deal

⁵²¹ N.64 (Perna) xvi

⁵²² Protocol Additional to the Geneva Conventions of 12 August 1949, and relating to the Protection of Victims of International Armed Conflicts (Protocol 1), 8 June 1977; Protocol Additional to the Geneva Conventions of 12 August 1949, and relating to the Protection of Victims of NIACs (Protocol 2), 8 June 1977

with civilian protection, as they only apply to IACs⁵²³ and CA3 is too general.⁵²⁴ Yet Protocol II remedies this protective gap to a certain extent.

Whilst important IHR standards have been affirmed at the international, as well as regional level, it is unclear which human rights are considered *ius cogens* “from which no deviation or derogation is permitted.”⁵²⁵ Moreover, IHR obligations exist only vis-à-vis the state, but do not extend to opposition groups. This results in non-state actors being insufficiently rendered accountable by IHR.

Opinion is divided about whether the relationship between IHR and IHL is complementary, concurrent or separate.⁵²⁶ Whilst it has become more accepted that the relationship between IHR and IHL is complementary, IHL is often considered the *lex specialis*. This undermines the ability of IHR to effectively protect civilians during NIACs.⁵²⁷ Furthermore, human rights derogations,⁵²⁸ limitations⁵²⁹ and reservations⁵³⁰ erode the effectiveness of IHR.⁵³¹

The domestic and international mechanisms are inadequate to safeguard civilians. Whilst international law requires states to conduct investigations and prosecute those, who have breached the IHR and IHL rules, it is unclear for which breaches this is the case.

The international oversight mechanism through the UN is problematic since the ‘responsibility to protect’ and the humanitarian intervention concepts contradict the UN

⁵²³ N.4 (Phuong) 45

⁵²⁴ N.15 (Jinks et al) 39

⁵²⁵ N.215 (Tomuschat) 44

⁵²⁶ N.197 (Fortin) 1433-1434; n.197 (Escorihuela) 303; n.197 (Heintze) 813; n.197 (Droege) 310

⁵²⁷ W. A. Schabas, *Lex specialis? Belt and Suspenders? The Parallel Operation of Human Rights Law and the Law of Armed Conflict, and the Conundrum of Jus Ad Bellum*, 40 *Israel Law Review* 2007, 592, 592

⁵²⁸ Also see Article 4(1) of the ICCPR

⁵²⁹ See for example Article 12(3) of the ICCPR; *Isayeva v Russia* [2005] 41 E.H.R.R. 38; also see *Ergi v Turkey* [1998] E.C.H.R. 59; n.247 (Tamura) 129-140

⁵³⁰ Article 2(1)(d) of the VCLT; H. V. Condä, *A Handbook of International Human Rights Terminology* (Nebraska, University of Nebraska Press 1999) 128

⁵³¹ Democratic Progress Institute, *International Human Rights in Armed Conflicts, Legal Factsheet*, 2014, 1, 1-2 <IHR human rights derogations, limitations reservations armed conflict> accessed 30 March 2015

Charter principles of non-intervention in the internal affairs of states and sovereign equality. The UN Charter does not spell out a power to authorise peacekeeping and this therefore depends on the consent of the state.

Moreover, the UNSC does not always enforce IHL and IHR due to geopolitical interests and the UNGA cannot act when the UNSC is seized by a matter. Even when it can act, its recommendations are non-binding. The power of other international bodies, such as the UN Secretary General, is too limited to make a real difference.

The ICJ deals with cases between states which practically bars NIACs from its jurisdiction and its advisory opinions are non-binding.

The jurisdiction of the ICC is very limited and does not permit that third party states, which support the warring parties and thereby fuel the conflict, can be pursued. Like with the ICJ, civilians cannot bring cases at the ICC. Also, the prosecutor's discretion to refer cases to the ICC and the ability of states to self-refer may not promote the appearance of independence.

The treaty-based bodies' main prerogative is IHR, as opposed to IHL; however, the complaint mechanisms are useful tools, but only if they were known to more individuals and resulted in binding, as opposed to non-binding decisions.⁵³²

Like the UNSC, the UN Human Rights Council is a political body, which has only got limited powers. The UN High Commissioner for Human Rights is stymied in its efforts due to its limited resources.

The services of the ICRC are not provided during all NIACs since these societies are only allowed to offer relief. Also, the ICRC primarily deals with IHL to the exclusion of IHR.

⁵³² United Nations Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, Human Rights Treaty Bodies - Individual Communications, 2015
<<http://www.ohchr.org/EN/HRBodies/TBPetitions/Pages/IndividualCommunications.aspx#whathappens>>
accessed 2nd September 2015

Furthermore, it has not developed a mechanism for civilians to enforce their IHL and IHR rights.

The ability of the permanent five security members to cast a veto when this in their strategic interest has resulted in inaction or delays, which has endangered civilians during NIACs.⁵³³

Truth commissions are ineffective in safeguarding civilians as they do not prevent suffering, but only investigate the aftermath. They often result in justice being foregone.

Moreover, the UN is not a party to the international treaties and can even evoke immunity.

This is problematic, particularly in light of reports about sexual abuse by UN peacekeepers.⁵³⁴ There thus exist an accountability problem which further heightens the vulnerability of civilians. Moreover, UN peacekeepers are not sent to every NIAC.

Protocol II is not equivocal about whether universal jurisdiction can be evoked when grave breaches are committed. Resultantly, countries make insufficient use of this.⁵³⁵ The fact that amnesties are commonly granted further enhances impunity.⁵³⁶

Furthermore, Protocol II does not expressly provide that states have to adopt legislation to investigate, prosecute and punish perpetrators and equally CA3 is silent on this. All thus depends on whether states adopt criminal laws to that effect. Consequently, victims can only very rarely lodge cases for IHR or IHL violations at their domestic courts, let alone seek

⁵³³ M. Ayoob, *Humanitarian Intervention and International Society*, 7 *Global Governance* 2001, 225, 225

⁵³⁴ N.439 (Lewis) 595

⁵³⁵ R. van Elst, *Implementing Universal Jurisdiction Over Grave Breaches of the Geneva Conventions*, 13(4) *Leiden Journal of International Law* 2000, 815, 815; see, for example, *Re Javor and others*, Cour de Cassation, Chambre Criminelle, 26 March 1996; International Federation for Human Rights (FIDH), *Implementing the principle of universal jurisdiction in France, Scope of the Universal Jurisdiction in France*, 1-12, 8 <https://www.fidh.org/IMG/pdf/universal_juris.pdf> accessed 13 April 2015; also see A. Cassese, *Is the Bell Tolling for Universality? A Plea for a Sensible Notion of Universal Jurisdiction*, 1 *Journal of International Criminal Justice* 2003, 589, 589; H.-P Gasser, 'The Changing Relationship between International Criminal Law, Human Rights Law and Humanitarian Law' in (eds) n.356 (Doria et al) 1116

⁵³⁶ N.472 (Ntoubandi) 223

compensation.⁵³⁷ In war-torn countries, the necessary institutional and judicial infrastructure may not be there to investigate and prosecute individuals. Also, it is unrealistic to expect that civilians can bring cases against those, who are still in power.

Furthermore, regional human rights courts are not established in all regions of the world. The scope of regional rights are different to IHRs and these courts do not deal with IHL matters, except to a very limited degree in certain cases. Hybrid courts and tribunals are not created for all NIACs. Moreover, their jurisdiction, including that of the ICC, is limited to only grave IHL and IHR breaches, thus enabling many to escape prosecution. This is particularly illustrated by the caseload of the ICC, which to date has only dealt with 22 cases.⁵³⁸

Furthermore, international environmental law is not integrated within IHL and IHR, despite the catastrophic impact environmental harm can have for civilians.

No independent monitoring, fact-finding and reporting process exists, which ensures that IHR and IHL norms are being adhered to.

Significantly, the current regime favours minimising harm over actual conflict prevention and thereby entrenches the idea of armed conflict within the normal status quo. As it is unrealistic to expect the disappearance of the war paradigm, it should at least be ensured that in respect of NIACs where there is a transnational element, for instance, any form of direct or indirect support from other countries, the more extensive IAC legal framework becomes triggered. This would at least avoid the difficult issues which arise from applying IHR to NIACs.

⁵³⁷ N.270 (Cohen and Shany) 41 and 47; also see Article 2(3) of the ICCPR

⁵³⁸ American Non-Governmental Organizations Coalition for the International Criminal Court, ICC Investigations & Cases, 2015 <<http://www.amicc.org/icc/cases>> accessed 1st September 2015

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